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Human Health Risk Assessment of Combined Exposures to Chemicals

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Challenges and Research Needs

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Preface

The Institute of Environmental Medicine (IMM), a department at Karolinska Institutet, Sweden, is an interdisciplinary research organization within the field of Environmental Medicine. Within the Institute, internationally competitive research in the fields of toxicology, environmental medicine and epidemiology is conducted.

Activities at the IMM are characterized by a broad range of expertise. The research is divided into four main research areas: occupational and environmental medicine, epidemiology, physiology and toxicology. An important part of the work at the IMM is to provide the governmental agencies with environmental health risk assessments as a basis for regulations and standard settings. The Institute also has broad international cooperation with the European Union (EU) and World Health Organization (WHO), including both research and risk assessment. Researchers at the IMM participate in more than 20 EU projects, as partners and/or coordinators, which provide a very wide network of international partners, including cooperation with several leading universities and research institutes.

Researchers at the IMM were invited to describe challenges associated with combined exposures to chemicals and human health risk assessment in their respective research fields. The authors that accepted the invitation have based their chapters on the current research and risk assessment activities in their respective areas. In some areas there are already well-established risk assessment methods, also for handling combined exposures, while for other areas this type of research has just begun. Accordingly, this report contains both broad overviews and state-of-the-art research. Each chapter briefly summarizes the state-of-the-art of risk assessment of combined exposures, but focus on research needs that may improve human health risk assessment (see Chapter 13 for conclusions, research and development needs).

This report is a collaboration between several scientists at the IMM. The conclusions have been discussed jointly. Professor Ulla Stenius, Professor Annika Hanberg and Associate Professor Marika Berglund have been in charge of the project and Dr Ilona Silins has coordinated it. The contributors to the various chapters are:

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1 INTRODUCTION

People are exposed to a wide range of chemicals (and other stressors) from multiple sources in their everyday lives. However, until now, the most common practice in chemical risk assessment has been to consider single chemicals separately and typically from a single source. Although important and significant findings have been made for individual chemicals and stressors, a far more realistic approach would be to evaluate risks at more complex exposure situations.

It has long been understood that chemicals interact in the body and that the combined exposure of chemicals could affect and change the health effects e.g. compared with exposure of the individual components. The joint actions of chemicals were already described in the 1930s (Bliss 1939). During the past few decades the problem of combined exposures and health risks has become more and more of a concern and regulatory authorities have further increased their attention to this issue (Monosson 2005). A number of scientific articles concerning the impact of combined exposures on human health have been published (see e.g. (Carpy et al. 2000; Rajapakse et al. 2002; Witorsch 2002; Kortenkamp et al. 2007; Kortenkamp 2008; Pohl and Abadin 2008)). One major concern is that low-dose exposures below or at a no-observed (adverse) effect level (NO(A)EL) can cause health effects when exposures are combined. Other scenarios are interactions of two or more components, which can result in synergy, where health effects become enhanced and magnified.

In this report we define “**combined exposure**” as the exposure to multiple chemicals by single or multiple routes.

A **mixture** is the combination of two or more chemicals with which organisms come in contact, either simultaneously or sequentially.

The problem is that adding more variables into the risk evaluation makes the risk assessment task more complicated. The increased complexity, in combination with data gaps has hampered the development in this field. Currently, the development and improvement of the risk assessment procedure for combined exposures is an important issue for many authorities (e.g. on-going activities in the WHO, USA and EU). An important aspect is to increase the research within this area.

Examples of some published reports/guidelines in this field are listed below:

- Risk assessment of combined exposure to multiple chemicals: A WHO/IPCS framework. Regulatory Toxicology and Pharmacology. Meek ME, Boobis AR, Crofton KM, Heinemeyer G, Van Raaij M, Vickers C, 2011.
- Hazard and Risk Assessment of Chemical Mixtures Under REACH, State of the Art, Gaps and Options for Improvement. Swedish Chemicals Agency, KEMI, PM 3/10 (Backhaus T, Blanck H, Faust M), 2010.
- Chemical Mixtures: A framework for assessing risks to human health (CR14), 2009. The Interdepartmental Group on Health Risks from Chemicals (IGHRC), Institute of Environmental and Health, Cranfield University, UK.
- State of the Art Report on Mixture Toxicity, Final report, Executive Summary, 22 December 2009, Responsible scientists; Kortenkamp A, Backhaus T, Faust M.
- Expert workshop on combination effects of chemicals, Workshop report, 28 - 30 January 2009, Hornbaek, Denmark.

- Concepts, methods and data sources for cumulative health risk assessment of multiple chemicals, exposures and effects: a resource document, The US Environmental Protection Agency (US EPA), 2007.
- Supplementary Guidance for Conducting Health Risk Assessment of Chemical Mixtures. US EPA/630/R-00/002, 2000.

It has been estimated that over 80,000 chemicals are available for sale and use in the USA and that 500–600 new chemicals are introduced to the market every year. In Europe, more than 100,000 chemicals are commercially available. However, for many of these chemicals human health effects are unknown (National Toxicology Program (NTP) 2009; Stewart and Carter 2009) and in terms of combined exposures, even less is known. From the perspective of sustainable development it is important to develop risk assessment for combined exposures.

In a recent report from President's Cancer Panel in 2009, it concludes that cancer risks from environmental agents and chemicals are seriously underestimated. According to the report, there is a growing body of evidence linking environmental exposure to cancer and for some cancers the incidence is increasing for unexplained reasons. The panel emphasizes that research on carcinogen's interactions and their effects during sensitive time windows (such as the prenatal period, early life and puberty) is underfunded. The panel proposes that more resources should be distributed to experimental and epidemiological research focusing on environmental cancer risks (President's Cancer Panel 2009).

1.1 Risk assessment of combined exposure

The few methods and models for handling combined exposures at regulatory level so far have been developed for chemical mixtures. There are ongoing activities to expand and develop methods which also include other factors for consideration (e.g. biological and physical agents) and adding a population focus. The US EPA has developed a framework for "cumulative risk assessment" (defined as the analysis of the combined risks from aggregate exposures (i.e. multiple route exposures) to multiple agents or stressors, where agents or stressors may include chemicals as well as biological or physical agents) (US EPA 2007). The US EPA framework includes concepts, methods and data sources to support development of cumulative risk guidance in the future.

The next section will summarize the most frequently used methods for handling combined exposures in risk assessment, mainly as chemical mixtures. Mixtures can be categorized in many ways, e.g. being simple or complex (US EPA 2000). Simple mixtures contain a well-defined number of components in contrast to complex mixtures. A mixture can be intentionally produced (e.g. manufactured mixtures), generated (e.g. by-products of processes such as fuel combustion, drinking water disinfection and cigarette smoking) or arise coincidentally. There are countless numbers of coincidental mixtures created in our environment (Sexton and Hattis 2007) and how these impact on human health is largely unknown. The exposure to a mixture can be either simultaneous or sequential.

1.1.1 Current methodology

There are three methods commonly mentioned in guidelines (US EPA 2000; Kortenkamp et al. 2009) and the method selected depends on the available data. The methods are: the whole mixture approach, the similar mixture approach and using data from individual components.

If data exist on the actual mixture of concern ("the whole mixture"), the risk assessment would be similar to a single substance assessment. The advantage of using data on the whole

mixture is that any interactions among the individual components will be reflected in the health effects data for the whole mixture. However, data on the whole mixture of concern are rarely available. Another approach is to use data for a similar mixture. Similar mixtures usually consist of the same chemicals, but in different proportions (ATSDR 2004).

If data on whole or similar mixtures are lacking, a common approach is to use data from the individual mixture components to predict the toxicity. There are two main models describing how chemicals in a mixture behave: by additivity (similar or independent actions) or by interaction. These models can be employed to predict the toxic effects of mixtures. The additivity concept is the most commonly used model.

Chemicals acting by similar/the same modes of action and/or at the same target cell or tissue, act in a dose-additive manner. Risk assessors also use the term “concentration addition”. The components of the mixture only differ in the concentrations needed to cause a toxic effect. Many risk assessment approaches are based on concentration addition, e.g. Hazard Index

Additivity is when the combined effect of two or more chemicals is equal to the sum of the effects of each substance.

(HI), Relative Potency Factors (RPF) and Toxicological Equivalence Factors (TEFs, which is a special case of RPF) (US EPA 2000). The other type of additivity is called “response addition” or “independent action”. Mixture components acting by

independent action have different modes of action or different target cells or tissues, but their end effects are additive (response additive). The independent action approach has often been applied for the risk assessment of carcinogens (US EPA 2000). Either method described above requires data for the individual components. For “concentration addition” the number and identity of components as well as concentrations and dose ratios are important information needed.

Chemicals can also interact with each other and thereby affect the toxicity of the mixture. The most common models are synergism (more than additive effect) and antagonism (less than additive effect).

Interaction is when two or more chemicals interact and the effects are either more than additive (**synergism**) or less than additive (**antagonism**).

For the dose addition approach, reference levels for individual chemicals are required. These values are usually based on the threshold levels at which no effects are observed in experimental studies, NO(A)ELs. However, these threshold levels are, by definition, statistically based, which means that non-significant effects (which may in fact be effects) are not considered. This means that the predicted toxicity, using a dose addition approach based on NO(A)ELs, sometimes may indicate, correctly or incorrectly, more than additivity (i.e. synergism).

Another approach to assess any uncertainty with mixtures and to protect against possible mixture effects would be to use a safety factor, a mixture assessment factor (US EPA 2000). This factor could be used if not all components are identified and if concentrations or concentration ratios are unknown. This has been suggested as a possible approach within this context: however it is not clear how much this approach has been used in practice.

1.2 How is risk assessment of combined exposure used by authorities today?

1.2.1 WHO – IPCS (International Programme on Chemical Safety)

In March 2007, the IPCS organized an international workshop on current issues in aggregate/cumulative risk assessment. Methods for assessing combined risks were discussed, which subsequently initiated the development of a framework for such assessments. A draft of this framework (WHO/IPCS Framework for Risk Assessment of Combined Exposures to Multiple Chemicals 2009) was made available for public and peer review comments. The IPCS suggests a tiered approach for risk assessments of chemical mixtures. It also suggests concentration/dose addition as a default method if no contradictory data is available (Meek et al. 2011).

1.2.2 European Union (EU)

In some parts of the EU legislation effects from exposure to multiple chemicals (mixtures) are considered, examples are the EU regulation on classification, labelling and packaging (CLP) of substances and mixtures, the regulation on plant protection products and the Cosmetics Directive (Council of the European Union 2009). Current risk assessment methodologies are based either on whole mixture testing or on component-based approaches assuming dose addition. However, for generated or coincidental mixtures and combined exposure there is currently no legislation that requires consideration for risk assessment purposes (Kortenkamp et al. 2009).

A recent report (Kortenkamp et al. 2009) calls for more consistent and clear directives for taking mixture toxicity into account in future EU legislation. This could facilitate the development of improved guidelines on chemical mixture risk assessments in the EU. The Council of Environment Ministers agreed to “[Conclusions on the combination effects of chemicals](#)” in December 2009. The Council of the European Union concludes, “the current legislation in this area needs to be assessed to how and whether it adequately addresses risks from exposure to multiple chemicals from different sources and pathways, and on this basis consider appropriate modifications, guidelines and assessment methods.” The council also encourages Member States to increase and improve research efforts in this area (Council of the European Union 2009).

The European Food Safety Authority (EFSA) has an ongoing commitment to develop risk assessment methodologies, especially for pesticides in food. The EFSA recently published a scientific opinion on risk assessment for a group of pesticides from the triazole group (EFSA 2009). The aim was to test different methodologies to assess the cumulative effects of pesticides in food. In 2006, the EFSA published a report called “Cumulative risk assessment of pesticides to human health: the way forward” (EFSA 2006). The EFSA uses a tiered approach, additivity concepts (such as concentration addition) and independent action, which are selected on a case-by-case manner.

One example of a mixed exposure that has received attention in the EU is indoor air. Indoor air contains a range of pollutants, at different exposure levels, with different possible health effects and differences in population sensitivity. The European Scientific Committee on Health and Environmental Risks (SCHER) mentions formaldehyde, carbon monoxide, nitrogen dioxide, benzene, naphthalene, environmental tobacco smoke, radon, lead and organophosphate pesticides as the components of most concern (Scientific Committee on Health and Environmental Risks (SCHER) 2007). Allergens, endotoxins, dampness, mould

and particles are other factors that contribute to a complex exposure situation (Dales et al. 2008).

1.2.3 US Environmental Protection Agency (US EPA)

The US EPA has relatively well-developed systems for handling combined exposure risk assessments. The US EPA has been working with chemical mixtures and risk assessment issues since the beginning of the 1970s and has developed a number of guidelines and frameworks related to this (US EPA 1986; US EPA 2000; US EPA 2003; US EPA 2007). The US EPA has also introduced the term “cumulative risk assessment”, which is defined as “the analysis, characterization and possible quantification of the combined risks from aggregate exposures (i.e. multiple route exposures) to multiple agents or stressors”. Included in this definition are other stressors than chemical, such as biological agents, physical agents (e.g. noise, nutritional status) or psychosocial aspects. These factors broaden the risk assessment further (US EPA 2003).

The use of mixture-specific toxicity data (whole mixture) is the preferred method used by the US EPA in the risk assessment of mixtures. If data on the whole mixture is not available the US EPA recommends combining toxicity information for each individual chemical in an additive manner (concentration/dose addition) unless there is convincing data to the contrary. Examples of three methods used by the US EPA for dose addition are the relative potency factors (RPFs), Toxicological Equivalence Factors (TEFs) and Hazard Index (HI). Response addition (independent action) is recommended by the US EPA for chemicals in a mixture that acts independently or has a different critical endpoint. The US EPA selects between concentration addition and independent action approaches on a case-by-case basis (US EPA 1986; US EPA 2000).

1.3 Research and development needs

Currently, most authorities (e.g. the US EPA, WHO and EU) try to summarize the current knowledge within the area; describe the methods that are currently used; develop guidelines, frameworks and other approaches to improve the process; identify research needs and knowledge gaps to be filled. The authorities conclude that more knowledge is needed for many parts of the risk assessment process, ranging from basic research to improved models and approaches that best predict potential health effects. In addition, the aspect of exposure duration needs to be considered as well as the knowledge about exposure sequences, which can influence the end effects. For example, exposure during childhood could affect a subsequent exposure in adulthood.

The US EPA lists several needs for the future risk assessments of mixtures. In general, more knowledge of specific modes of action of chemicals is required. In addition, statistical and mathematical models, including extrapolation models (for mixtures that have not been tested) need to be further developed and their use should be expanded. Short-term toxicity assays and uncertainty methods also require further development in order to evaluate several scenarios for mixtures that will vary in their exact composition (US EPA 2000).

The US EPA also states that there is a need for better and more information about typical exposure situations. For example, which are the chemical mixtures present in human tissues? What are the relevant combined exposures of the human population? To test all possible mixtures that can arise in the environment and in our bodies is not possible. Instead, priority mixtures can be identified for which research efforts focus on (US EPA 2000; Kortenkamp et al. 2009). Some priority mixtures have already been identified and are relatively well studied.

For example, much focus has been on groups of chemicals like pesticides, polycyclic aromatic compounds (PAHs) and dioxins. Other examples of priority mixtures are heavy metals, endocrine disrupters and diesel exhaust (Stewart and Carter 2009).

There is concern that low-dose exposure (below or around threshold levels) can cause health effects when exposures are combined. Mixture effects can only be excluded if all mixture components act entirely independently (which may not be the case in reality) and if all components are present at levels that do not cause any effects (which is not possible to confirm experimentally) (Backhaus et al. 2010). In all other situations the effects of mixtures should be considered.

2 EXPOSURE

2.1 Exposure to single or multiple chemicals

2.1.1 Basic exposure assessment

Humans are simultaneously exposed to a wide variety of chemicals in the general environment, from food, air, water, and from consumer products. The exposure takes place at various locations: indoors and outdoors, at home, at the workplace and at other locations, and during transport. The time period of exposure varies from acute to life-long, and it can be continuous or intermittent, short-term or long-term. The exposure distribution of the general population includes different subgroups, such as children, elderly people, and the occupationally exposed, who can be more or less sensitive, and more or less exposed, i.e. more or less at risk than the rest of the population. The essence of exposure is the contact of a chemical (or other stressor) and a target (e.g. a human being). Exposure assessment is the process of estimating or measuring the magnitude, frequency and duration of the contact to an agent, along with the number and characteristics of the exposed population. The main objective of the exposure assessment is to obtain realistic and quantitative estimates of exposure, stratified for different subgroups of the population.

A major challenge in exposure assessment is to determine the total exposure, via all relevant routes and pathways, in various groups of the population, and for relevant time frames. Not only the duration of an exposure but also the timing and the sequence of exposure, e.g. if it takes place during a sensitive time window, needs to be considered. The lag time between exposure and effect must also be considered when linking an exposure with an effect.

Human exposure to chemicals in the environment is controlled not only by the occurrence of the chemicals, but also by human behaviour, physiological characteristics and different external factors. The default values or quantifiable statistics used to describe this information are called exposure factors. Exposure factors include information on drinking water volume consumed, soil ingestion, inhalation rates, dermal factors (including skin area and soil adherence factors), consumption of certain food items and breast milk, activity patterns, body weight and use of consumer products, and are ideally stratified for age and gender. For skin exposure to sensitizers and irritants, see Chapter 8.

The exposure to chemicals can be measured directly, at the contact site of an individual (personal exposure), or indirectly, by calculating/modelling the exposure. Indirect exposure is typically calculated from data on chemical concentrations in various exposure media which is multiplied with measures of contact rates or exposure factors.

Exposure assessments are conducted with different objectives and with different requirements relating to the required level of detail. A tiered approach is useful. A highly-exposed individual, representing the worst-case situation, is normally used as the first tier. If such an assessment shows no risk, no more detail is needed.

2.1.2 Deterministic vs probabilistic exposure assessment

The deterministic approach (based on point estimates) is typically used for screening purposes and worst-case estimations, in which conservative point estimates for the exposure parameters are used. Exposure factors have been developed for a number of variables and for both adults and children by the US EPA (US EPA 1997; US EPA 2008). When there is a need for a more realistic exposure scenario or a need to know the variability (the natural variation) in exposure

levels the probabilistic approach can be used. This approach is based on representative distributions of exposure factors/variables, which are not always at hand. Therefore, efforts should be made to generate or gather such data.

2.1.3 Exposure scenarios

Exposure scenarios are a tool to help the assessor develop estimates of exposure, dose, and risk. An exposure scenario generally includes facts, data, assumptions, inferences, and sometimes, professional judgment about how the exposure takes place. Creating an exposure scenario is a step-by-step procedure and involves the analysis of all available information and of increasing data quality and precision. The exposure scenario should include all possible and relevant exposure sources, pathways and routes, for different groups of the population, and for different time frames. Development of typical exposure scenarios, e.g. for contaminated sites, is highly necessary for the development of models for combined exposures.

2.1.4 Aggregated and cumulative exposure assessment

The exposure to a single chemical from all possible routes is called aggregate exposure or combined exposure to a single chemical. The exposure to multiple chemicals by multiple routes is called cumulative exposure.

The following definitions have been proposed for aggregate and cumulative exposure assessment by WHO (WHO 2009).

Aggregate exposure (single chemical, all routes): The demographic, spatial and temporal characteristics of exposure to a single chemical through all relevant pathways (e.g. food, water, residential uses, occupational) and routes (e.g. oral, dermal, inhalation).

Cumulative exposure (multiple chemicals, multiple routes): Defines the aggregate exposure to multiple chemicals.

In aggregated/cumulative exposure assessment, chemicals sharing a common effect are grouped together to determine the total exposure. In this report we define “**combined exposure**” as the exposure to multiple chemicals by single or multiple routes.

2.1.5 Exposure models

Modelling of human exposure is typically used for chemical emissions into the environment (indirect exposure). Models in this group include CalTOX, CSOIL, E-FaST, EUSES, SHEDS and TRIM. There are also models that have been developed to estimate pesticide exposures in agriculture and at home (CALENDEX, CARES, LifeLine, Rex2000).

In the EU, the risk assessment for new and existing industrial chemicals is performed according to the Technical Guidance Documents (TGDs) (European Commission 2003). In the EU-TGDs methods for aggregate exposure of consumers are described. It includes exposure from the environment, through the use of consumer products and at the workplace. Exposures from different scenarios/pathways, sources and routes are added (taking into account differences in bioavailability of the chemical different exposure routes). In the risk characterization, the total daily intake estimated is then compared with a no-effect level for humans at the right spatial and temporal scales (typically long-term exposure).

2.1.6 Step-by-step procedure for combined exposure assessments

Assessment of the combined exposure to multiple chemicals via single or multiple routes is preferably carried out as a step-by-step procedure. If it is reasonable to believe that the exposure is very low, there is no need for detailed information, and vice versa. The tiered approach for exposure assessment proposed by WHO/IPCS (Meek et al. 2011) is briefly described below:

For a Tier 1 assessment, summation of deterministic estimates of exposure for all components of the *assessment group* (group of chemicals that can be assessed together) may suffice as a basis for comparison with a measure of hazard to determine whether further assessment is necessary. These estimates are commonly based on broad, conservative scenarios addressing a range of somewhat similar uses with limited numbers of parameters being included.

In Tier 2 assessments, deterministic estimation of exposure is refined, with incorporation of increasing amounts of measured data. Scenarios are better defined and specific. Models may incorporate additional parameters and, although estimates are still considered conservative, they are believed to be more realistic, incorporating more data. Multiple sources are often taken into account by summation (this approach introduces additional conservatism).

In Tier 3 assessments, estimates of exposure are probabilistic in nature, taking into account distributions of exposure factors or exposure data. This approach requires representative information on exposure for the scenarios of interest for the relevant populations for different uses and across populations. Models at this level of complexity often include multiple source exposures.

2.1.7 Research and Development needs

There is a need for better exposure information for combined exposure assessment. This includes concurrent exposures to multiple chemicals or where exposure at different times leads to overlap in the time course of effects as a consequence of their respective toxicokinetics (TK) and/or toxicodynamics.

There is a general lack of accurate exposure information suitable for risk assessment. Harmonized methods are necessary to enable compilation of data and comparability between studies/data sets. A European initiative to develop harmonized guidelines for human biomonitoring was initiated some years ago, Consortium to Perform Human Biomonitoring on a European Scale, (COPHES), and is currently implemented with support from EU FP7. A feasibility study, Democophes, is implemented in 16 Member States, with the aim to test out the harmonized guidelines developed within COPHES. The IMM is the Swedish representative for these two projects.

Detailed exposure studies are quite costly and labour intensive. Therefore, development of exposure models is highly necessary. Development of validated exposure models, both deterministic and probabilistic, for long-term and short-term exposure, is needed. Validated models have to be based on real and accurate data. An inventory of data suitable for exposure assessment may reveal both useful data and data gaps. One source of human exposure data is the Swedish national health-related environmental monitoring programme which provides individual exposure and dose data for common, and to some extent, emerging chemicals. Data from other environmental monitoring programmes can provide data on chemical concentrations in air, water and some other types of environmental media, including the

screening programme (Miljögiftssamordning). Data on chemical concentrations in foods are available from the National Food Administration.

There is a need to group chemicals for combined exposure assessment purposes. Combined exposure assessment can only involve chemicals that share a common endpoint or effect. This could be based on (of increasing order of refinement) structural considerations (common structure of the chemicals), Absorption, Distribution, Metabolism and Excretion (ADME) considerations (delivery to target tissue, common metabolite, biomonitoring), mechanism considerations (interaction at molecular target(s), common molecular target), mode of action (MOA, cellular response, common key event), and response (organ response, common tissue).

One strategy would be to group chemicals (develop scenarios) that are typically and commonly present together in the environment, at typical concentrations. One example is chemical mixtures typically present at contaminated sites (e.g. metals, PAHs), depending on the type of former activities. Other examples are pesticide residues in fruits and chemical mixtures in indoor air.

Specific research needs:

- Develop harmonized methods for combined human exposure assessment (including biomonitoring) for the generation of comparable data and thereby a larger database.
- Inventory and gathering of representative exposure data and exposure factors suitable for modelling, stratified by age and gender.
- Develop typical exposure scenarios and exposure models.
- Grouping of chemicals based on common endpoint or effect that are typically present together in the environment.

2.2 Occupational retrospective exposure

In the occupational life, individuals are exposed to chemical substances in levels 2–3 magnitudes higher than large groups in the general population. In addition, exposures were significantly higher in the past. The occupational exposure is different from the ambient exposure through its exposure variability, e.g. five 8-hour shifts a week. Occupational related exposure (ORE) is usually combined exposure, e.g. the working environment in a steel production plant. In the epidemiological context, ORE is determined by using either direct or indirect methods.

2.2.1 Characterization of occupational exposure – direct methods

ORE is usually determined by personal monitoring in the breathing zone. Unfortunately, this is not done on a sufficiently large scale at present. Measurements follow established international guidelines. A special sampling strategy is required to characterize a person's exposure and compare it with exposures for other workers with similar tasks at the same workplace. Usually the measurement takes only 1–2 days per subject. This therefore requires the right selection of volunteers to be representative (other workers in the same occupation and job). Factors that need consideration are day-to-day variability (*within* worker variability), as well as variability between workers in the same occupation (*between* worker variability). Variability strategies emerged at the end of the 1980s–1990s, based on theories developed by S. Rappaport (Rappaport et al. 1993) in the U.S. These were further developed in Europe by H. Kromhout (Kromhout et al. 1993). These methods have recently begun to be used in Sweden and are mostly used in occupational hygiene research.

Since ORE is mostly combined exposure, multiple compounds/chemicals are simultaneously measured. Thus, all particulate substances are sampled in the same filter and in the chemical analysis the composition of the particles is analysed. Different particle sizes require different methods (filters, cyclones, pre-separator). Sometimes different airborne contaminations are sampled, e.g. particles/gases as diesel particular matter/nitrogen dioxide (Lewne et al. 2007), or particles/solvents like wood dust/terpenes (Hagstrom et al. 2008). Solvents are sampled in an adsorbent and further analysed both qualitatively and quantitatively. The same procedure can be used for gases.

Direct-acting instruments (real-time monitoring) are available for dusts, solvents and gases. Such analyses could help to increase the knowledge of continued intervention at the workplace. Moreover, this method gives the opportunity to determine if exposure peaks occur, which offers interesting opportunities for studying the uptake of various target organs. Person-borne measurement equipment can be gravimetric, which gives a daily average of the components. The daily average can easily be compared with Swedish Threshold Limit Values (TLV), issued by the Swedish Work Environment Authority (Arbetsmiljöverket 2005).

More measurements were performed during the 1970s–1990s compared with today, but many measurements were poorly executed and inadequate. The use of computer-based measurement databases (exposure records) started a few years ago in Sweden. Databases in Finland and Norway are based on a similar occupational exposure panorama and have exposure records that go far back in time. This is important when retrospective exposure assessments are performed. Data of this kind are available in a Finnish job-exposure matrix, FINJEM (Hang 2005), from which exposure to 23 carcinogens have been converted into Swedish conditions for 300 occupations (Kauppinen et al. 2009).

ORE measurements can be combined with biological sampling to validate the methods and to calculate the exposure dose.

International collaboration is important for the further improvement of methods for multiple ORE exposures. For example, in one EU project estimations on the total number of occupationally exposed workers for lung carcinogenic substances were assessed (Peters et al. 2011). The Unit of Occupational Medicine at the IMM collaborated with the International Agency for Research on Cancer (IARC) in Lyon, in a project on lung cancer and multiple exposures, SYNERGY (Olsson et al. 2010) (see Chapter 6.2). Another international project, INTEROCC (Tongeren 2009), based in Barcelona, studied multi-chemical exposures and interactions with electromagnetic field.

2.2.2 Indirect methods

Sufficient exposure information is often lacking and in population-based case-control studies there is often limited information regarding details of individuals' work activities. In these cases indirect methods are used. The major difficulty is to get valid data about the past work exposures. In census studies it is often only possible to have access to information on occupation through the Swedish Census. A useful tool can be a job-exposure matrix (JEM). In a generic JEM, occupations are used as surrogates for exposure. JEMs have been used since the early 1980s and have been further developed since then. Finland has constructed FINJEM (Hang 2005) and it is continuously updated. A Nordic JEM has recently evolved from FINJEM and contains quantitative exposure data since 1945 for 23 chemical substances spread over 313 internationally classified occupations (Kauppinen et al. 2009). In a joint

Nordic project (Pukkala et al. 2009), Nordic Occupational Cancer (NOCCA) studied chemical exposure and the cause of 2.4 million Nordic inhabitants' diagnosed with cancer using the Cancer environment register (CER). A Nordic JEM was developed by an expert team including IMM members.

Expert judgment is another way to estimate the ORE, especially retrospective exposure (Kauppinen et al. 2000). The classification is based on production data, engineering control and work activities. These ratings can be semi-quantitative, but development is now moving towards estimating quantitative exposure times using reconstructions.

2.2.3 Research and development needs

International collaboration is necessary to expand and improve the models developed in Sweden. In the US, the statistical models for exposure estimates, like Bayesian statistic models, are used, while in Europe deterministic models are more commonly used.

International collaboration studies give the opportunity to link occupational exposure assessments with toxicological research and further increase collaboration on the subject of combined chemical exposure. Validation of expert judgment models is in progress and there is an increasing need for this type of evaluation for the future. Furthermore, we need to build up a digital exposure database in Sweden, containing all exposure data collected during the measuring programmes in the 1970s, 1980s and 1990s.

3 BIOMARKERS

3.1 Biomarkers of exposure, effects, and susceptibility

This chapter is partly based on a recent review article (Silins and Högberg 2011) published in the *International Journal of Environmental Research and Public Health*.

Biomarkers employed in human health studies are commonly divided into three classes: biomarkers of exposure, effect and susceptibility. Biomarkers of exposure comprise measurements of the parent compound, metabolites, and DNA- or protein adducts and reflect internal doses, the biologically effective dose or target dose. Effect biomarkers could be cellular alterations, such as an altered expression of metabolic enzymes, but could also include markers for early pathological alterations in complex disease developments, such as mutations or preneoplastic lesions. Susceptibility biomarkers show an often constitutive capacity of an individual to respond to specific exposures.

Biomarkers of exposure are preferably specific to the chemicals of exposure, while biomarkers of effect are often unspecific to the agent in question (Scherer 2005). This simple view suggests that effect biomarkers should have a higher potential to reflect complex exposures and should also have the ability to include combined and sequential exposures over time. Additionally, the use of effect biomarkers in studies of complex exposures could support the identification of both the active components of the combined exposure, as well as the consequences of specific mixture exposures.

An exposure biomarker that has been used in several studies on complex mixtures of PAHs is the excretion of 1-hydroxypyrene in urine. PAHs are a group of chemicals formed as complex mixtures in many combustion processes. Many PAHs have been shown to be animal carcinogens, via a genotoxic mode of action, and are of great toxicological concern. Benzo(a)pyrene (B(a)P) is the most well-studied PAH and it was recently classified by the International Agency for Research on Cancer (IARC) as a human carcinogen (International Agency for Research on Cancer (IARC) 2009). The detection and quantification of PAHs in air samples is a challenging task, and B(a)P is frequently used as a marker for all PAHs. This approach is not ideal, as the composition may differ with the sources and with time since formation. To overcome these problems, many studies have used 1-hydroxypyrene excretion in urine as a biomarker for PAH exposure. Pyrene is one of the most common hydrocarbons in PAH mixtures and is considered a more sensitive biomarker than B(a)P. For example, biomonitoring of 1-hydroxypyrene in urine has been used in studies of workers in aluminium smelter plants and in workers exposed to asphalt fumes or creosote (Elovaara et al. 1995; Alexandrie et al. 2000; McClean et al. 2004).

DNA adducts are often considered to be biomarkers of exposure, whereas gene mutations and chromosomal alterations are often considered biomarkers of early biological effects in cancer development (Jarabek et al. 2009). Other examples of biomarkers of effect of importance for complex mixtures are measurements of alterations in biological systems, e.g. acetylcholinesterase inhibition by mixtures or combined exposure to organophosphate pesticides (Ryan et al. 2007).

3.2 Biomonitoring common mechanisms of action: example of oxidative stress

Low levels of oxidative stress may reflect the normal metabolism, but oxidative stress is a common pathological process and might have a role in the development of many diseases. For example, inflammation and oxidative stress are involved in chronic diseases such as

atherosclerosis and tissue fibroses, and are also seen in many lung diseases. Another disease often associated with oxidative stress is cancer. Many metals, including arsenic and selenium as well as several xenobiotics, including dioxins, polychlorinated biphenyls (PCBs) and PAHs and other carcinogens, have been shown to cause oxidative stress. Consequently, monitoring oxidative stress could be a useful approach to study interactions between numerous toxicants. Nevertheless, it should be kept in mind that oxidative stress is sometimes an important causative factor and sometimes only a bystander in an agent's, or a mixture's, toxicological profile.

Endogenous DNA adducts that result from oxidative stress are always present in genomic DNA and could be generated as artefacts during sample preparation. This non-zero background causes uncertainty when risks are extrapolated from hazardous chemicals that produce oxidative stress that is important for toxicity and/or carcinogenicity. Base oxidation is one of the most common insults to DNA and frequently used biomonitoring markers are end products of oxidative DNA damage, e.g. 8-oxo-7,8-dihydro-2'-deoxyguanosine and malondialdehyde-dG adducts (Taioli et al. 2007).

When examining the role of oxidative stress in the pathogenesis of disease, and when using oxidative stress as biomarker, a collection of biomarkers, specific for the different types of oxidative stress-induced damages, might be useful (Swenberg et al. 2008).

3.3 Biomarkers and cancer

The area of biomarkers reflecting the exposure and effect of carcinogens is relatively well explored. A possible motivation for this attention is the knowledge that the development of cancer takes many years and that there is a requirement for early markers of effect: 10–40 years of latency between the first exposure and diagnosis is commonly anticipated. In addition, interactions between different types of carcinogens, e.g. initiators and promoters and their interactions over time have been well characterized in animals. These circumstances have led to the development of many biomarkers of exposure and effect, and fortunately, many of the effect biomarkers could be suitable for monitoring combined exposures.

Genotoxic xenobiotics cause direct DNA damage, which can be biomonitoring as a single endpoint, although the type of DNA damage may differ. However, it is important to remember that not all DNA adducts are equally prone to cause mutations. The mutagenic ability may depend on, e.g. the type of adduct, the capacity for DNA repair and the cell type. Furthermore, DNA adducts are also formed endogenously, from normal metabolic or dietary components (Jarabek et al. 2009). Useful endpoints for the biomonitoring of complex mixtures comprise the so-called comet assay, which measures DNA strand breaks. Surrogate target cells include samples of blood lymphocytes or buccal leucocytes. The buccal leucocytes approach has been used for biomonitoring asphalt workers exposed to complex mixtures of asphalt fumes (Lindberg et al. 2008). Measurements of micronuclei is another biomonitoring method commonly used for assessing mixture exposure (Fimognari et al. 2005; Mielzynska et al. 2006; Bortoli et al. 2009).

Mutations as biomarkers of cancer represent more specific endpoints than DNA damage. Mutations can occur in reporter genes, such as Hypoxanthine-guanine PhosphoRibosyl Transferase (HPRT) (genes not associated to cancer development, but used as surrogates since they are relatively easily assessed), or more specifically, in oncogenes or tumour suppressor genes. The mutation spectra in the tumour suppressor p53 have been extensively studied. Some mutations have been claimed to reflect carcinogen specificity, such as the codon 249

mutations caused by aflatoxin exposure (Besaratnia et al. 2009). Many other “hot-spot” mutations in the p53 gene have not been linked with single carcinogenic compounds but may reflect the effects of many xenobiotics, and should be appropriate for the biomonitoring of mixtures. Other mutations have been associated with oxidative stress and may thus reflect endogenous oxidative stress induced e.g. by inflammation or by oxidative stress inducing xenobiotics or viruses (Hussain et al. 2007).

We have found no literature on general biomarkers suitable for non-mutagenic carcinogens. Enzyme induction, cell proliferation or the inhibition of gap junction intracellular communication and modulation of apoptosis are examples of common modes of action for these types of carcinogens (Hattis et al. 2009). These endpoints have been mostly studied in animal and cell experiments. It can be added that a large array of signalling molecules are critical for non-mutagenic carcinogenic effects and that genomic and proteomic approaches should be suitable for future development in this research area. Such endpoints should help to find novel potential biomarkers for non-mutagenic carcinogenic effects of chemicals in humans (Watson and Mutti 2004).

3.4 Biomarkers and endocrine disrupting chemicals

Recent studies indicate that endocrine disrupting chemicals may interact in complex ways (for a recent review see (Diamanti-Kandarakis et al. 2009)). In particular, endocrine disrupting chemicals may interact over time, in a similar way to that of many carcinogens. The endocrine disrupting mode of action has caused concern, especially as even low exposure during foetal or early life periods might be involved. This characteristic will certainly complicate the detection of harmful interactions in epidemiological studies and there is a great need for reliable biomarkers of effect. Unfortunately, published biomonitoring data on endocrine disrupting chemicals mainly focus on agent-specific exposure markers, not on effect markers.

Phthalates are ubiquitous xenobiotics found in many plastic products, cosmetics etc. Many phthalates have shown endocrine disrupting and anti-androgenic properties in animal studies, but usually these phthalates have been investigated one at a time. However, in a recent study on newborn boys, their mothers were monitored during pregnancy for prenatal phthalate exposure, and several phthalates derived from domestic and lifestyle-associated exposures were biomonitoring (Swan et al. 2005). The global presence of phthalates suggests that analysing metabolites in urine is a way to avoid contamination problems. A combined phthalate exposure index was defined for each pregnant woman and it was found that this index of combined phthalate exposure correlated to the anogenital distance (AGD). A reduction of the AGD has previously been associated with anti-androgen effects of hormonal disruption in animal studies. This study suggests that the exposure of pregnant women to phthalates in the daily environment may have effects on foetal development. However, additional studies showing similar effects of similar exposures are needed for more definitive conclusions and the effect of single phthalates versus the combined effect of all analysed phthalates remains to be studied. It can be noted that the index for combined exposure gave a stronger significance compared with the significance for any single phthalates, suggesting a major contribution by the combined action.

Oestrogenicity caused by combined exposures of xenoestrogens has been determined by measuring cell proliferation in breast cancer cell lines treated with human adipose tissue samples (the so-called E-screen) (Fernandez et al. 2008). This procedure has also been applied when analysing xenoestrogenic extracts from human placenta (Lopez-Espinosa et al. 2009), this technique was used in a case-control study. Fifty newborn boys with cryptorchism and/or

hypospadias were compared with 114 boys without malformations. Of these, 72% of the cases and 54% of the controls had detectable xenoestrogens in their placentas and this difference was significant ($p < 0.05$) (Fernandez et al. 2007). This study supports the idea that xenoestrogens measured in placenta extract can be used as a biomarker of exposure in studies on hormonal disruption.

We have not been able to find many studies describing the monitoring of pathological effects caused by endocrine disruptors in humans. This may relate to the fact that most studies so far have been employing experimental animal models. However, with the purpose of shortening animal studies, effect markers for malformations have been studied in animals (Christiansen et al. 2008). After *in utero* and postnatal exposure to mixtures of anti-androgens the AGD, nipple retention and a dysgenesis score were measured. It was found that at least the AGD at birth predicted later developed hypospadias.

The hypothesis of a testicular dysgenesis syndrome (TDS) is based on several observations on early manifestations at birth, such as cryptorchism and hypospadias and later development of infertility and germ cell cancer in testes in young men. A possible role of endocrine disrupting chemicals has been discussed, but firm evidence seems to be lacking in humans. In animal studies, however, it has been shown that combined exposures to low doses, unable to induce effects of their own, can result in a reduced AGD (Sharpe and Skakkebaek 2008). It is thus feasible that future studies on testicular cancer or infertility may use early manifestations of TDS as effect biomarkers of chemicals causing endocrine disruption.

3.5 Research and development needs

The field of biomarkers needs continuous development of new and improved biomarkers, both for single and combined chemical exposures. For endocrine disrupting chemicals, more efforts are needed to find good, reliable effect biomarkers, both for single and combined exposures (see Chapter 9 for further information). Finding a single, suitable biomarker for combined exposures may be a challenging task. Instead, a collection of biomarkers has been suggested for complex mixtures, each individual biomarker will provide some of the ideal characteristics of a specific biomarker (Ryan et al. 2007).

For carcinogens, both exposure and effect biomarkers have been developed, but these need further improvement. For example, an increased understanding of the connections between exposure, biomarkers and health effects is generally required. To measure DNA adducts and mutations as biomarkers has been a common approach for evaluating exposures to carcinogens. However, cancer-causing chemicals can also alter gene expression by epigenetic mechanisms, and epigenetic alterations have the potential to become important biomarkers in future applications. Importantly, epigenetic changes may often be of a reversible nature and detecting such early changes can not only be used for risk assessment purposes but also benefit both therapeutic as well as preventive measures (Wild 2009).

Other potentially interesting targets for biomonitoring are telomeres. These DNA stretches form the end of chromosomes and are shortened every time a cell divides, and it has been suggested that telomere attrition might be used for biomonitoring purposes. Many types of chemically induced stresses may induce these types of effects. Measuring telomere attrition might be an informative marker for many types of complex chemical exposures.

In conclusion, even though a number of studies evaluating the use of biomarkers and biomonitoring for combined or mixed exposures have been found, further development in this

area is required. Still, there are questions to answer about the relation of biomarkers to health effects, and to the levels and pathways of exposure. More information is needed to investigate what biomarker data indicate. Other future goals would be to find more specific biomarkers for combined exposure and develop methods to improve biomarker sampling.

4 TOXICOKINETICS

4.1 Introduction

Toxicokinetics (TK) is the mathematical description of the uptake and disposition of a chemical in the body. TK may be seen as the first link in the dose – effect continuum (Figure 4.1). It is often divided in four processes: Absorption, Distribution, Metabolism and Excretion (ADME). Toxicokinetic modelling is usually carried out by describing the time course of the amount or concentration of the parent substance and its metabolites in one or several body compartments.

A major reason for addressing TK is the well-established notion that the likelihood or magnitude of the toxic effect is directly related to the target dose, i.e. the amount of the chemical, or its active metabolite(s), at specific targets in the body. Thus, any change in the TK, e.g. because of combined exposure, may also affect the dose-response and dose-effect relationships and, hence, toxicity. Such changes may be investigated by using toxicokinetic or metabolic models, be it *in vivo*, *in vitro* or *in silico* (computer modelling) (Johanson 2010).

Figure 4.1 The dose - effect continuum.

Combined exposures to two or more chemicals may result in inhibition or induction of biotransformation enzymes, transporters and plasma transport proteins, as well as substrate depletion. All these changes may, more or less markedly, alter TK and toxicity. Many other factors that may significantly alter biotransformation and other toxicokinetic processes, as well as toxicity, are not considered specifically as combined exposure and are therefore not discussed here in detail. These factors include: route, pattern and duration of exposure, physical exercise, diet, smoking, alcohol intake and other life-style factors, starvation, obesity, body build, genetic disposition and disease. For examples of these types of interactions with inhalation exposure to different organic solvents, as well as combined exposures to two or more solvents, see the review by Lof and Johanson (Lof and Johanson 1998).

4.2 Physiologically Based Pharmacokinetic (PBPK) models

Of particular interest in toxicokinetic analyses of combined exposures and resulting interactions is PBPK, also called Physiologically-Based Toxicokinetic (PBTk) modelling. PBPK models (Figure 4.2) attempt to predict the disposition of a chemical in the body from relevant quantitative data on physiology and anatomy as well as biochemical data. Examples of physiological data are organ volumes, blood flows, and body growth; biochemical data, include tissue partitioning, protein binding, metabolic pathways and metabolic rates of the chemical. In such models, *in vitro* data on e.g. enzyme capacity (V_{max}), affinity (K_m) and inhibition are conveniently incorporated.

Although conceptually promising, PBPK modelling has, so far, only been used to a limited extent to address combined exposures. Thus, only around 50 publications were encountered in scientific literature (PubMed search in November 2010, pharmaceutical drugs not included). The reason is probably lack of biochemical interaction data.

Figure 4.2 Schematic representation of a simple inhalation PBPK model including one metabolite level.

Conceptual models

The median effect principle is based on the assumption that the dose-effect relationships of many chemical and biological processes, specifically those relating to ligand-enzyme and receptor interactions, can be described by the Hill equation. According to this equation, the dose-effect curve is defined by the median dose (e.g. ED₅₀) and a slope factor (n).

The Hill equation can be expanded to include the interactive effects of chemicals in a mixture for different types of individual dose-effect shapes: negatively cooperative ($n < 1$), non-cooperative (Michaelis-menten type, $n = 1$), positively cooperative (sigmoidal, $n > 1$) and interactions: mutually exclusive, mutually non-exclusive etc. (Chou and Talalay 1984; el-Masri et al. 1997).

The outcome of the experiments analysed by median effect principles may further be elucidated by response surface methodologies (RSM), see e.g. (Solana et al. 1987; el-Masri et al. 1997). RSM addresses the relations between several explanatory variables and one or more response variables. As illustrated in Figure 4.3, RSM may be used to explore and visualize dose-response or dose-effect relationships and identify synergistic dose domains. It is very important to identify synergistic effects, as these result in stronger toxic effects (or higher risks) than would be expected from the commonly used default assumption of additivity. Although difficult to visualize graphically, the same methodology may be used for more than three dimensions, e.g. multiple toxic effects and/or more than two chemicals.

Figure 4.3 Example of a simple response surface diagram. In this example the toxic effect (response variable) depends on the combined dose of two the chemicals, A and B (explanatory variables). The inclined plane to the left and the peak to the right represent additive and synergistic dose domains, respectively.

4.3 Effects on absorption

4.3.1 Inhalation

The respiratory uptake of chemical gases and vapours depends, apart from the ambient air level, mainly on the pulmonary ventilation, cardiac output and blood solubility (air: blood partition coefficient). Co-exposure to a (second set of) chemical(s) that affects the ventilation and/or the cardiac output will thus also affect the respiratory uptake. However, such effects are only expected to occur at high levels that are not likely to be encountered in environmental exposure scenarios. The blood solubility can theoretically be affected by chemicals (and by fat-rich diets!) that alter the blood lipid content. Again, this effect is not very likely at in environmental exposure levels.

For poor blood-soluble chemicals, equilibrium between inhaled air and pulmonary venous blood is rapidly attained. Therefore, the elimination from blood is also of importance for the uptake in the lungs. Hence, inhibition/induction of biotransformation enzymes resulting in decreased/increased metabolism will also result in decreased/increased pulmonary absorption of the inhaled chemicals.

4.3.2 Dermal route

The dermal absorption of chemicals may increase or decrease upon combined exposure to a number of alcohols, glycols and glycol ethers, sulfoxides, fatty acids, surfactants and detergents, terpenes, amides and pyrrolidones (for review see, e.g. (Kaushik et al. 2008)) and chemical permeation enhancers are of great interest in transdermal drug delivery, e.g. with nicotine and scopolamine patches. The mechanisms include changes in skin: water partitioning, morphological changes in stratum corneum or deeper skin layers, or combinations thereof. The solvent dimethyl sulfoxide (DMSO) is maybe the most well-known dermal permeation enhancer, but even water and increased skin humidity enhances the penetration. Fossil fuels and organic solvents, such as acetone, may also disrupt the skin barrier so that the permeability for any other chemical is increased.

4.3.3 Oral route

The systemic bioavailability of an orally ingested chemical may increase or decrease, due to the inhibition or induction, respectively, of hepatic biotransformation enzymes by a second chemical. These effects are a consequence of the hepato-gastro-intestinal anatomy, with the portal vein transporting nutrients (and absorbed chemicals) from the gastrointestinal to the liver before they enter the systemic circulation.

Nutritional status will affect the gastrointestinal uptake of metals. For example, it is known that low body iron stores lead to an up-regulation of the intestinal divalent metal transporter (DMT1), which leads to an increased absorption of both Fe²⁺ and Cd²⁺, as well as other divalent metal ions (Garrick et al. 2003). DMT1 is regulated by iron deficiency.

4.4 Effects on distribution

The distribution of chemical in the organism may be influenced by substances that affect, for example (list is not complete, examples are overlapping):

- Binding to or induction of transporter, plasma and tissue proteins.
- Blood-brain barrier.
- Blood lipid content.
- Bone uptake, storage and release.
- Fat diffusion permeation.
- Enterohepatic cycling.
- Local or regional blood flow.
- Tissue: blood, blood: air, plasma: blood and plasma: air partitioning.
- Uptake and binding in erythrocytes.

Little has been done to study these factors. However, with regard to partitioning, Beliveau et al. (Beliveau et al. 2001) found in an experimental study a minor effect ($\leq 15\%$) on the blood: air partition coefficient of halomethanes when added jointly to rat blood, as compared to individually. Further, Abu-Qare and Abou-Donia (Abu-Qare and Abou-Donia 2003) showed that concurrent administration of the two pesticides permethrin and N,N-diethyl-meta-toluamide (DEET) disrupted the blood-brain barrier in rats and changed the *in vivo* and *in vitro* metabolism and pharmacokinetic profiles of the individual compounds.

Lee et al. (Lee et al. 2002; Lee et al. 2007) modelled the transfer of the PCB congener PCB153 from the mother to the pups in mice during lactation and how it was affected by PCB126. Parameters assumed to be altered by the co-exposure were the liver: blood partition coefficient and the fat diffusion permeation constant. However, the scientific basis for these assumptions is weak and aryl hydrocarbon receptor (AhR)-related factors probably play a key role.

Lee et al. (Lee et al. 2009) showed that co-exposure of methyl mercury-treated mice to PCB congeners increased the albumin content in blood and that this in turn caused increased methyl mercury levels in the blood, brain, kidney and carcass. The experiments further showed that the PCB co-exposure increased the lactational transfer of methyl mercury to the pups. PBPK simulations could well describe the experimental results.

4.5 Effects on metabolism

Chemicals can affect their mutual metabolism by inhibition or induction. Inhibition can be:

- Direct, competitive and reversible.
- Irreversible (e.g. reactive intermediate inactivation of a cytochrome P450 (CYP) or tight binding by an essentially irreversible inhibitor (that can also be formed during metabolism)) or
- Indirect by depletion of substrates or cofactors.

Inhibition can have negative consequences as the half-life of the parent (or other) chemical is extended and the target dose increased. In addition, a change of metabolite profile to more toxic products is conceivable. It should be kept in mind, however, that inhibitory interactions could have positive consequences, such as to lower the concentrations of toxic metabolites.

4.5.1 Inhibition after low-dose exposures

Low-dose exposure is defined here as realistic levels of environmental contaminants encountered in human plasma (calculated from Swedish and Inuit blood samples) (Sjodin et al. 2000; Tan et al. 2008). These range between 100 pM to 10 nM for individual compounds such as PCBs, hydroxy-PCBs, hexachlorobutadiene (HCB), hexachlorocyclohexane (HCH), pentachlorophenol (PCP) and polybrominated diphenyl ethers (PBDE) and up to 100 nM for perfluoro-octanesulfonate (PFOS). When added together the combined concentrations often approach the 100-nM range and vary considerably between individuals and geographic location. At these low doses substrate or cofactor depletion is not likely to be significant considering the metabolism of these compounds is most often very slow (otherwise they would not accumulate). Low-concentration compounds that are metabolized rapidly are cleared rapidly and therefore are less likely to cause toxicity unless they form reactive intermediates or strong irreversible inhibitors or otherwise potent toxic metabolites.

Reversible inhibition

Given that Phase I and certain Phase II enzyme concentrations in liver are in the micromolar range (calculated from (van Ommen et al. 1990; Lupton et al. 2009)), and thus are likely to exceed the levels of chemicals in low-dose exposure mixtures, direct, competitive and reversible inhibition is not likely to be of consequence.

When substrate concentration is comparable to, or higher than, enzyme concentration it is still likely that the substrate concentration will not saturate the enzyme¹. Also, in this case, there is no interaction since there is an ample amount of free enzyme. In summary, low concentrations of substrates do not yield direct metabolic interaction (regardless of the relation to enzyme concentration). The same argument also holds for low concentrations of compounds that are not substrates but inhibitors.

On the other hand, when substrate concentrations become saturating, the rates strongly influence each other in the form of mutual inhibition. Thus, in the case of less abundant biotransformation enzymes that display a very high affinity for their substrates, interactions

¹ Substrate concentrations below K_m are most likely, since K_m values in the nM range are rarely encountered for biotransformation enzymes. When substrate concentrations are below K_m most of the enzyme is free and turnover is governed by $v = k_{cat}/K_m * [E]_{free}$. Under all conditions the relative rates for substrate conversion of two substrates in a mixture is governed by their concentrations and their k_{cat}/K_m values as given by $v_a/v_b = (k_{cat}/K_{m_a}[A])/(k_{cat}/K_{m_b}[B])$ (Fersht 1999). When $S \ll K_m$ or when $E \gg S$ the rates are directly given by $v = k_{cat}/K_m * [E]_{free}$ in which case there is no interaction.

are likely. Thus, it is of interest to define classes of chemicals and corresponding metabolic pathways for which saturation occurs.

Irreversible inhibition

In the case a mixture contains compounds that are or become irreversible inhibitors (either by direct tight binding or after metabolic activation, including reactive intermediates that bind covalently), there will be a certain rate of inactivation of the enzyme depending on the dose of the chemical. If this rate exceeds the rate of new synthesis of the enzyme in question activity will decline. Thus, compounds that lead to irreversible inhibition could have profound effects on enzymes of biotransformation that are present at low concentrations and have long half-lives.

4.5.2 Inhibition by high-dose exposures

Literature is ripe with examples of metabolic interaction after high-dose exposures. For instance, a way to treat methanol poisoning is to inhibit its conversion to a toxic metabolite by giving ethanol that competes for the metabolic enzymes. Drug-drug interactions are, of course, of primary concern sometimes leading to severe adverse effects (Guengerich 1997; Uetrecht 2008). Also, high exposure of mixtures of industrial chemicals (e.g. solvents) does result in metabolic interaction (Lof and Johanson 1998). These examples highlight the mechanism and provide proof in principle, but they do not provide a good basis for evaluating the metabolic effects, or lack thereof, of complex mixtures.

One can make an arbitrary distinction between involuntary (and unavoidable) exposure to low levels of environmental chemicals resulting in an increased complexity of body burden as opposed to the voluntary intake of drugs and food-stuffs containing a plethora of highly abundant molecular species that are presumed to be more or less safe. The latter high concentration compounds will have a profound effect on the metabolism of the former. Thus, the consideration of cocktail effects will have to be made from the perspective of total biotransformation. Although not the focus here, this is a true challenge that needs to be addressed once metabolic interactions among low-dose environmental contaminants are better understood.

4.5.3 Induction

Biotransformation capacity is highly dynamic and regulated by many mechanisms. Exposure to mixtures of both high and low concentration does have an impact. It is important to note that the lack of metabolic interaction in biotransformation at low doses described above does not correspond to a corresponding scenario in terms of induction. On the contrary, for induction every added molecule can have an effect and depending on the dose-response curve this effect might be more than additive. Specific mechanisms are elaborated in the example of the AhR (see Chapter 5 for further information).

4.6 Effects on excretion

The excretion of chemical in the organism may be influenced by substances that affect:

- Renal excretion
- Biliary excretion
- Lactation
- Exhalation

Urinary excretion is driven by glomerular filtration, diffusion, and tubular excretion and reabsorption. It is difficult to imagine that the two first mechanisms would be affected by combined exposures. However, substances that alter the binding to plasma proteins or haemoglobin and/or uptake in red blood cells will thereby also alter the unbound fraction and, hence, the excretion via glomerular filtration. Tubular excretion and reabsorption may theoretically be affected in the same way as any enzyme process.

Biliary excretion is mainly driven by active excretion and can be affected in the same way as enzyme processes. The biliary excretion may, however, be modified by enterohepatic circulation so that, in the end, distribution rather than excretion is affected.

Combined exposure of rats to cadmium and nickel in drinking water containing these elements, over a period of 90 days, resulted in increased biliary excretion of cadmium and reduced biliary excretion of nickel (Cikrt et al. 1992). Similarly, intraperitoneal administration of selenite or selenate decreased the urinary and biliary excretion of mercury in HgCl-treated rats (Cikrt and Bencko 1989).

In contrast to renal and biliary excretion and due to the formation of milk, lipophilic compounds may be excreted via lactation. Here the mechanism will differ, so that increased binding to plasma proteins may result in increased rather than decreased excretion. This was shown by Lee et al. (Lee et al. 2009), as described above.

The exhalation of chemicals can be considered the reverse process of inhalation uptake (see section 4.3).

With the exception of a few studies on lactational transfer (see section 4.4) and biliary excretion, no studies addressing these issues were found in scientific literature.

4.7 Research and development needs

- Literature survey of ADME processes: which studies have been carried out (experimental, PBPK, chemical combinations) and what did they show (type and magnitude of interaction on relative to dose, exposure or concentration)?
- Chemical-specific interaction studies *in vitro*?
- PBPK simulation studies: expected magnitude of interaction relative to dose or exposure.
- Monte Carlo PBPK studies to address variable mixed exposures.
- Integrated approaches, including PBPK, Monte Carlo simulations, the median effect principle and response surface methodologies.
- Systematic study of the metabolic interactions of low-dose chemical mixtures.
- Determine the reactive intermediate burden caused by chemical mixtures.
- Develop computational tools that can predict metabolic interactions and reactive intermediate burden.

5 THE ARYL HYDROCARBON RECEPTOR (AhR) AND CYTOCHROME P4501A1

5.1 Introduction

Chemicals in mixtures can modify their mutual metabolism by inhibition or induction, as described above (see section 4.5). This chapter will illustrate the impact of cytochrome P4501A1 (CYP1A1) induction and inhibition on the toxicity of combined chemical exposures and potential consequences for risk assessment. The induction of CYPs by compounds that activate the AhR, has been discussed in the fields of cancer research, toxicology, pharmacology, and risk assessment over the past half century because these enzymes are involved in the metabolism of many xenobiotic pollutants and drugs (Nebert and Dalton 2006).

An introduction to the biology of the AhR is given here, since this receptor protein has a central role in risk assessment of some carcinogens and endocrine disrupting chemicals that are described later in this document, especially the dioxin-like substances and their effects on foetal development of the reproductive, nervous and immune system (see Chapter 10 for further information).

5.2 The AhR is a physiological sensor

The AhR binds small endogenous and exogenous molecules (ligands). It is regarded as an important homeostatic transcriptional regulator within physiological and pathophysiological processes, including xenobiotic metabolism (Nebert and Dalton 2006), perinatal growth (Fernandez-Salguero et al. 1995; Mimura et al. 1997), fertility (Abbott et al. 1999; Baba et al. 2005), liver and vascular development (Schmidt et al. 1996; Lahvis et al. 2000; Lund et al. 2003), autoimmunity (Veldhoen et al. 2008), haematopoiesis (Schmidt et al. 1996; Singh et al. 2010) and cancer (Shimizu et al. 2000). The AhR belongs to the basic helix-loop-helix (bHLH) Per-Arnt-Sim (PAS) family of transcription factors. Many PAS proteins are involved in regulating responses to environmental signals in the tissue such as light, hypoxia, oxidation-reduction status, and circadian rhythms (McIntosh et al. 2010). The AhR is highly conserved in evolution and is present in most cell types. A wide spectrum of physiological effects has been documented in AhR-knockout animals and in animals exposed to substances that interfere with the AhR pathway (for a recent update on AhR signalling, see (Fujii-Kuriyama and Kawajiri 2010)). This suggests that interference with the endogenous regulation of the AhR pathway may disturb different physiological outcomes in different tissues and cell types.

The AhR regulates the expression of a number of metabolism/detoxification enzymes, the most highly upregulated enzyme being the CYP1A1 enzyme. Activation of the AhR is commonly assayed at the CYP1A1 mRNA, protein or enzyme activity level. High-throughput screening assays that respond to binding of the AhR to constructs that activate a reporter gene in stably transfected cells are also commonly used. A problem with cell-based AhR assays is that they also respond to high-affinity AhR ligands present as contaminants in the cell culture medium.

Figure 5.1 The tryptophan photoproduct 6-formylindolo[3,2-*b*]carbazole (FICZ) is a proposed endogenous AhR ligand. FICZ has the highest affinity for binding to the AhR of all compounds tested, it is an ideal substrate for the CYP1A1/1A2/1B1 enzymes and it is present in humans (references in (Wincent et al. 2009)).

The endogenous AhR ligand/s is not yet established, although many low-molecular-weight chemicals have been shown to qualify as endogenous or physiological AhR ligands. The proposed high-affinity ligands include the tryptophan photoproduct 6-formylindolo[3,2-*b*]carbazole (FICZ), the compound with the highest affinity for binding to the AhR, as well as other compounds derived from the amino acid tryptophan (Nguyen and Bradfield 2008). FICZ is also an ideal substrate for CYP1A1/1A2 and 1B1 and participates in an autoregulatory feedback that maintains its own steady-state concentrations at low levels (Wincent et al. 2009). Xenobiotic compounds representing different chemical classes that mimic the endogenous AhR ligands can bind to the receptor and activate CYP1A1 and other AhR-regulated genes. But it has also been established that several endogenous and exogenous molecules can induce CYP1A1 without having the capacity to bind to the AhR as exemplified in all-*trans*-retinoic acid, melatonin, arsenic and cadmium, omeprazole, nonylphenol, bisphenol A, phthalates and non-coplanar PCBs.

5.3 The consequences of CYP1A1 induction/inhibition in mixture exposure

CYP1A1 is one of the best characterized xenobiotic-metabolizing enzymes which is often discussed in connection with the formation of reactive electrophilic metabolites that can react with DNA or protein. For example, PAHs stimulate their own metabolism because they bind to the AhR and activate CYP1A1.

The efficient induction of CYP1 enzymes in the liver, primarily the enzymes CYP1A1, 1A2 and 1B1, following treatment with carcinogenic PAHs and heterocyclic aromatic amines (HAAs), were described in the 1950s. Since that discovery, the induction of CYP1 enzymes has been considered a mode of action of importance for toxicity and human risk assessment. Many compounds have been regarded as harmful because they activate the AhR and induce CYP1 enzymes, and therefore possibly increase the metabolism of PAHs and HAAs into ultimate carcinogens. As a consequence, inhibition of CYP1 enzymes has been considered protective. In fact, both chemopreventive and anticancer properties of phytochemicals have been attributed to their capacity to inhibit CYP1A1 (Galati and O'Brien 2004). The hypothesis that high CYP1 (1A1, 1A2 and 1B1) activity mediates toxicity of PAHs appears mechanistically attractive based on the capacity of CYP1 enzymes to activate PAHs and HAAs to reactive metabolites that can form DNA adducts and lead to gene mutations and cellular transformation. However, it has more recently been reported that detoxification by CYP1A1 is also important for protection against various deleterious effects of PAHs, including cancer (Nebert and Dalton 2006; Ma and Lu 2007). CYP1A1 induction can thus be considered both as a detrimental and a beneficial response, which complicates risk assessment of complex mixtures that contain both inhibitors and inducers of CYP1 enzymes.

Several recent *in vivo* studies with CYP1A1 knock-out mice show that CYP1A1 enzymes protect against PAH and HAA carcinogenicity by speeding up their clearance from the body (reviewed in (Ma and Lu 2007). Actually, the early studies by the Millers and other scientists in the 1950s also showed that the CYP1 induction by 3-methylcholantrene and other PAHs inhibited the tumorigenicity of HAAs (Miller et al. 1958).

In addition, new eco-toxicological findings regarding heart deformities in early life stages of fish exposed to mixtures containing CYP1 inducers and inhibitors point to the detrimental effects of inhibitors on other toxicological endpoints than cancer (Billiard et al. 2008). Inhibitors like fluoranthene and *alpha*-naphthoflavone were found, opposite to what was expected, to increase cardiovascular toxicity in fish (Wassenberg and Di Giulio 2004). This

effect could partly be explained by lowered clearance of toxic PAHs, but other modes of action, including dysregulation of physiological signalling via AhR-regulated pathways cannot be ruled out.

5.4 Research and development needs

Mixtures containing halogenated and/or non-halogenated PAHs are difficult to risk assess because their modes of action are complex and only partially understood. The combined action of different types of substances in mixtures that interfere with the AhR and/or the CYP1 enzymes via different mechanisms may lead to an under-estimation of risks if the risk assessment is based on additivity. The persistent activation of the AhR by metabolically inert ligands, such as dioxins, can be assessed in a dose-additive manner since they cause similar effects and show parallel dose-response curves. But there is no simple way to assess the combined risks from other classes of halogenated and non-halogenated PAHs that activate AhR signalling but lack the similarity in responses that make additive risk assessment possible for dioxin-like chemicals. The situation becomes even more complicated if mixtures contain other agents with CYP1A1-modifying capacity, such as plastic monomers and additives, heavy metals and products of incomplete combustion.

Understanding the role of the AhR and its endogenous ligand/s in the induction and inhibition of CYP1A1 is important for improving risk assessments of mixtures of many types of toxic and endocrine disrupting chemicals interfering with this pathway. Importantly, the same agents seem to be able to enhance or inhibit the mutual effects depending upon the circumstances of their interactions. It is also plausible that individual susceptibility to chemicals that occur in mixtures will differ depending on polymorphic CYP1A1 genotype variants in the human population. Therefore, more mechanistic research is needed to understand how environmental pollutants disturb normal biological processes. Such knowledge will improve the risk assessment of complex exposures.

6 CANCER

6.1 Cancer mechanisms, initiation and promotion

6.1.1 General background

The development of a tumour takes many years and it is generally accepted that it is a multistep process. The process may start as a mutational event. A mutation might be inherited or a somatic mutation induced by reactive endogenous metabolites or by xenobiotics. It may also start as an epigenetic event that is inheritable from cell to cell. Crucial for the carcinogenic process is clonal expansion of the “initiated” cells. This means that cells carrying a mutation or an inheritable epigenetic alteration divide and multiply so that a clone of altered cells is formed. Additional mutational or epigenetic alterations are required for the development of a clinically manifest tumour.

It can be assumed that an initiating event, in many cases predispose for additional genetic events. For example, an initiating event might lead to an increased cell growth either by stimulating inappropriate cell divisions or by preventing programmed cell death or apoptosis. Safeguarding mechanisms are normally operating in a healthy cell, but one or several additional mutations may occur, by chance or by influence, e.g. xenobiotics. It has been estimated that 5–8 alterations in basic cellular functions have to be permanently deranged in a cell before it can behave as a fully malignant cancer cell. Other estimates indicate that about 13 signalling pathways, each including many genes and proteins, are commonly affected in carcinogenic processes, and that mutations or epigenetic alterations that “drive” the development of tumours are to be found in these 13 signalling pathways.

It is well established that xenobiotics can speed up carcinogenesis and that xenobiotics can do this in several ways. This scenario actually opens up for interactions between xenobiotics. Indeed, experimental studies performed 30–50 years ago clearly indicated a multistep process and laid the ground for our current understanding on how tumours develop. These experimental studies showed that “initiators” of the carcinogenic process were not carcinogenic in sufficiently low doses, but readily induced tumours if combined with other types of xenobiotics, called “promoters”. A third group of chemicals were also defined which selectively facilitated the “progression” of tumour development. Later work has shown that most initiators mainly act by inducing mutations by a direct interaction with DNA, in low doses. Promoters mainly act facilitating clonal expansion of initiated cells. This effect can be obtained in many different ways, e.g. by selectively inhibiting apoptosis or stimulating proliferation of cells carrying the “initiating” mutation or epigenetic alteration. In general terms, the interaction between initiators and promoters can be described as an exposure applying selective pressure for clones initiated by an earlier exposure (Nelson and Kelsey 2002).

Figure 6.1 The classical animal experimental model showing synergistic effects between different carcinogenic chemicals.

The scenario for tumour development sketched by the initiation-promoter experiments has been supported by later studies using genetically engineered mice. One such study on exocrine pancreatic cancer development (Ji et al. 2009) shows that excessive expression of the

oncogene K-ras resulted in the senescence and death of affected cells. This illustrates that mutations of K-ras alone will not cause cancer. However, senescent cells may release inflammatory mediators which can induce inflammation and oxidative stress which may eventually mutate other genes. The tumour suppressor gene p53 is one gene that causes senescence, and if this gene is inactivated, e.g. by oxidative stress-induced mutations, tumours can rapidly develop. This illustrates a four-step scenario for cancer development: 1) ras activation by mutation, 2) cellular senescence, 3) inflammation and 4) p53 inactivation by mutation.

The experimental literature on “initiation” and “promotion” of carcinogenesis contains classical examples of dramatic interactions. As already mentioned, initiators were found to induce no tumours when given in sufficiently low doses, but gave tumours when combined with a promoter. Furthermore, promoters given without an initiating event did not give tumours either. These experiments are thus examples showing potentiating interactions, where $0 + 0 = 1$, but also showing synergism where $1 + 1 = > 2$. Most importantly, however, these experimental studies have convincingly shown that interactions are also to be expected in human carcinogenesis. They show that interactions may occur after exposure to complex mixtures such as tobacco smoke, diesel exhaust or work with special combinations of chemicals. They also show that interactions may occur after sequential exposure of interacting xenobiotics. For example, childhood exposure, or even exposure before birth, may interact with exposures much later in life.

Risk associations to such scenarios are not easily captured in epidemiological studies. The relative rarity of many tumour types, their long latency period, and the very complex exposure and lifestyle scenarios humans normally encounter during the long latency period, rise problems, and the epidemiological literature available has been more limited in providing clear evidence for carcinogenic interactions. Perhaps many contradictory results in epidemiological studies can be explained by undetected interactions between several xenobiotics and/or lifestyle factors. Here we will summarize two relatively well-studied examples, namely asbestos and silica, and their interactions with other carcinogenic xenobiotics.

A recent document, produced by President’s Cancer Panel in the US, concludes that environmental cancer risks (cancer caused by chemicals) are greatly underestimated and suggests numerous actions to reduce these risks (President's Cancer Panel 2009). The panel emphasizes that research in the field of carcinogen interactions and sensitive time windows is underfunded and suggest that more resources are allocated to experimental and epidemiological research focusing on environmental cancer risks.

6.1.2 Asbestos and lung cancer

Asbestos interacting with tobacco smoke is a classic example of carcinogen interactions. Possibly the first observation was based on epidemiological data, showing that asbestos exposure alone was associated with a 5-fold increase, smoking alone with a 10-fold increase and exposures to both agents associated with 50-fold increases in lung cancer (Selikoff et al. 1968). Additional studies have indicated a so-called multiplicative interaction (instead of an additive interaction), which was interpreted to suggest that the two agents acted independently in separate steps in the multistep carcinogenic process (Vainio and Boffetta 1994). More recent studies indicate a joint effect between additivity and multiplicatively (Gustavsson et al. 2002). In efforts to explain the interaction between asbestos and tobacco smoke in mechanistic terms some emphasis has been put on tumour localization (lower lobes) and

tumour type (adenocarcinoma) as an indication of this interaction, but the support has weakened as this pattern has also been seen more recently among non-asbestos exposed lung cancer cases, e.g. among former smokers (Nelson and Kelsey 2002).

Molecular analysis will perhaps be more informative and some progress has been reported. Two lines of mechanistic reasoning have been supported. One reasoning implies that both asbestos and tobacco smoke carcinogens induce similar types of mutations or DNA alterations giving rise to similar effects. Thus, it has been shown that asbestos can induce clastogenic effects and large DNA deletions and that asbestos exposure can be related to homozygous deletions of the p16/CDKN2A gene. Heavy smoking, on the other hand, may inactivate the same gene via epigenetic hyper-methylations in the promoter region (Andujar et al. 2010). Other studies suggest that asbestos may enhance mutational effects in k-ras or p53 genes of tobacco smoke carcinogens, such as PAHs (Loli et al. 2004). This latter scenario is supported by data showing that, e.g. asbestos can bind PAH and increase local or intracellular exposure to critical targets. In addition to this, several studies indicate a role for inflammation in asbestos carcinogenesis (Vainio and Boffetta 1994; van Helden et al. 2009).

6.1.3 Silica and lung cancer

It is of interest to compare the literature on joint effects of asbestos with that of joint effects of silica dust. Silica dust was classified as a human carcinogen (group 1) by the IARC in 1997, but it was noted that not all exposures could be associated with lung cancer. Controversies still exist regarding the role of silicosis and exposure levels that can be associated with silicosis (Brown 2009). Most studies, however, indicate low or no risk among non-silicosis patients (Pelucchi et al. 2006; Erren et al. 2009). At least two risk assessments are based on the assumption that exposures not giving rise to silicosis do not constitute a significant risk for lung cancer (Health Safety Executive 2003; Scientific Committee on Occupational Exposure Limits (SCOEL) 2003). In a recent Swedish study on iron ore miners in Kiruna it is concluded that quartz exposure, but not radon or diesel exhaust, was associated with lung cancer. Significantly increased risks were observed even below 2 mg years/m³ (Bergdahl et al. 2010). An effect at this low level might have been influenced by an interaction with iron, as it has been shown that iron can catalyse free radical reactions and that iron-contaminated silica is more cytotoxic (Hamilton et al. 2008).

The interaction between silica and tobacco smoke has been discussed in several epidemiological studies. A recent study indicates that it can be described as a joint effect between additive and multiplicative (Vida et al. 2010). A similar conclusion has been reached regarding asbestos and smoking (Gustavsson et al. 2002). An earlier meta-analysis provided evidence for an additive interaction, but not for a multiplicative interaction (Kurihara and Wada 2004).

Mechanistic studies indicate several pathways leading to toxicity, inflammation and immune modifications (Hamilton et al. 2008). They include effects on lung surfactant production, receptor-mediated binding and toxicity in alveolar macrophages, increased free radical production and lysosomal damage. None of these pathways are excluding other pathways and they may work in tandem (Kurihara and Wada 2004). Most mechanistic studies focus on more short-term toxicities induced by silica and their specific relationship to cancer is not clarified. There is, however, a clear causal connection between short-term effects such as inflammation and silicosis, and between silicosis and lung cancer. Indeed, human studies show increased frequencies of micronuclei among workers exposed to silica-containing dust (Demircigil et al. 2010). Furthermore, and perhaps unrelated to any of the above-mentioned toxicity pathways,

silicosis patients exhibit aberrant promoter hypermethylation in cancer-related genes such as p16INK4a (Umemura et al. 2008). Interestingly, the same gene is also hypermethylated among heavy smokers (Andujar et al. 2010), so this common effect might be a base for interactions.

It is obvious that many other carcinogens may interact in this process. Documented interactions in well-controlled animal studies include effects of the radioactive contrast medium thorotrast (Spiethoff et al. 1992) and with benzo[a]pyrene (Niemeier et al. 1986). An epidemiological study suggests that numerous occupational and non-occupational risk factors, including arsenic and PAH, interact in a complex way with silica in the lung carcinogenic process (Cocco et al. 2001). A recent publication suggests the use of quartz-contaminated coal for in-house fires, and thus interactions between PAHs and silica can explain the highest local mortality rate in lung cancer among women in China (Large et al. 2009). In a review from 2007, it is concluded that differences in the production of reactive oxygen species (ROS) and TNF- α by alveolar macrophages may account for the great variation in lung cancer risk among epidemiological studies (Cocco et al. 2007).

6.2 An ongoing epidemiological multicentre study of interaction in lung carcinogenesis

Many work environments involve complex exposure patterns, and over a work history many workers may be exposed to more than one carcinogen. Typical exposures of coexisting occupational carcinogens include radon and quartz, asbestos and PAHs, or chromium and nickel compounds. Animal experimental data show that combinations of carcinogens may interact in different ways, from a purely additive effect to supra-multiplicative effect. Findings from animal studies can rarely be extrapolated to humans, due to variations in sensitivity and mechanisms of action. There are very few epidemiological studies on the interaction between two or more occupational carcinogens, as pointed out above (see section 6.1). Most studies involving exposure data on several occupational carcinogens focus on one exposure and treat the others as potential confounders. There is a rather large literature on the combined effect of occupational exposure to asbestos and tobacco smoking, investigating the nature of the interaction in detail. The reason for the lack of studies addressing the interactive effect of several occupational carcinogens is mainly that very large studies with detailed data on occupational exposures are needed. Considering the strong effect and potential confounding from tobacco smoking, detailed data on tobacco smoking is also needed.

Several population-based case-control studies on occupational lung cancer have been published over the past 10 years, mainly from Europe and Canada. These studies are relatively similar in design, with a complete occupational history and a life-time smoking history, in addition to other variables. Although several of these studies are large, none of them are of a sufficient size to effectively assess the interaction between several occupational carcinogens. In addition, large databases of exposure levels of several carcinogens in various occupations have been compiled over the past 10 years, allowing a more detailed assessment of exposure.

Against this background, the German insurance organization for compensation of occupational diseases (HVBG) decided to finance a pooling and reanalysis of a number of existing case-control studies from Europe and Canada. The JEM technique is used to assess exposures in a valid way. This study, SYNERGY, is coordinated by the IARC in Lyon, France, and is aimed to contribute to the currently very limited knowledge on the interaction of combined occupational exposures in human lung carcinogenesis. This knowledge is needed

for effective prevention strategies as well as for the compensation of occupational diseases. In Germany, as well as in several other countries, the compensation is based on evaluation of the effect of single carcinogens, regardless of whether the effect is augmented by other coexisting occupational exposures.

Currently, SYNERGY holds information on 13,304 cases of lung cancer and 16,282 controls from 11 case-control studies conducted in Germany, France, the Netherlands, the United Kingdom, Italy, Sweden, the Czech Republic, Hungary, Poland, Romania, Russia, Slovakia and Canada. Sweden contributes with data from LUCAS – Lung Cancer in Stockholm – with data on 1,014 cases and 2,307 controls (Gustavsson et al. 2002). Large efforts have been made to harmonize exposure data, including the recoding of occupational histories and smoking data, to obtain a valid pooled analysis.

In addition to studying interaction, this large database is also used to study single carcinogens for which there is a significant lack of knowledge about carcinogenic effects, or a lack of dose-response data. Recently, analyses have been completed showing an association between exposure to diesel motor exhaust and lung cancer risk and a dose-response pattern (Olsson et al. 2010). Analyses of lung cancer risk in cooks and kitchen workers are under way. Analyses of interactive effects will start during 2011. First on the agenda is an analysis of the joint effect of exposure to radon and quartz, and asbestos and PAHs.

6.3 Cancer risk assessment of mixtures of polycyclic aromatic compounds (PAHs)

Cancer risk assessment of PAHs is complicated due to the complexity of PAH mixtures present. At the same time, there are few data available for PAH mixtures and chemical analysis data of mixtures is limited. Many PAHs are known or suspected carcinogens. Benzo[*a*]pyrene (B(a)P) has been well characterized toxicologically, while less information is available for most other PAHs and practically no information about how different PAHs interact. There are thus very few toxicological data available for whole PAH mixtures and on potential interactions among individual components within the mixture.

In some cases B(a)P is used as an indicator of carcinogenic PAHs in complex mixtures (European Parliament and Council 2004), but this will probably underestimate the carcinogenic potential of mixtures due to the presence of other carcinogenic compounds. In other cases *toxic equivalency factors* (TEFs) are used for risk assessment of PAH mixtures. TEF-values are used as a practical tool in risk assessment and reflect the relative potency of PAHs compared with the potency of B(a)P. TEFs for individual PAH (relative to B(a)P) summarize the B(a)P equivalent dose assuming additivity for their carcinogenic effect. TEF values are based on available data and variable endpoints (Bostrom et al. 2002). One example where TEF values are used in practical risk assessment is “Site Specific Guidelines for Contaminated Soils” (Swedish EPA). Often risk assessment of PAHs is related to the concentration of a few compounds. At the same time, PAH-containing mixtures tend to be very complex and, in cases where polluted soils have been analyzed, they exhibit considerable variation in their PAH profiles and the B(a)P levels do not correlate to levels of other PAHs (Lundstedt et al. 2006).

There are several uncertainties in applying the TEF-concept for PAHs. The TEF-concept requires the same mechanism of action and additivity is assumed, but PAHs are heterogeneous and their carcinogenic mechanisms differ widely. Multiple modes of actions

for carcinogenesis are thus possible. For example, it is clear that different carcinogenic PAHs induce different types of DNA binding, DNA adducts and mutations. Furthermore, different PAHs have different levels of carcinogenic potency. Some are genotoxic and bind to DNA, while others have tumour promotive effects. The ability of certain PAHs to act as initiators as well as tumour promoters may increase their carcinogenic potency and induce synergistic effects. The assumption of additivity may thus not be valid. In cases where contaminated soil has been analyzed, sites exhibit considerable variation in their PAH profiles, and there is often a mixture of genotoxic and tumour promotive PAHs (Lundstedt et al. 2006). An important factor for the variation of PAH profiles at contaminated sites is that high molecular weight PAHs are more persistent than smaller PAHs. Furthermore, metals in the soil can affect the degradation of PAHs.

Another factor is that TEF-values do not account for interactions. Interactions between different PAHs might confer considerable synergistic effects. Thus, animal studies have shown that the B(a)P as an indicator may reflect as little as 20% of the cancer potency of such mixtures (Gaylor et al. 2000). This is supported by the data where TEF-values were applied to cancer data (Schneider et al. 2002). The authors conclude that TEF values do not adequately describe the potency of the PAH mixture and this can lead to underestimations regarding the carcinogenic potency of most mixtures. This can partly be explained by the fact that TEF-values are derived from different types of cancer studies and for many PAHs there is a total lack of cancer data. For others, TEFs are derived by combining across multiple exposure routes, species, sexes and tumour types. This means, e.g. that B(a)P data derived from oral exposure study is compared with data from skin or subcutaneous application (Schneider et al. 2002). Furthermore, PAH mixtures induce tumours in organs where B(a)P do not induce tumours, and this fact further supports an important role of interactions.

One contributing factor for underestimating risk is that tumour promotive and non-genotoxic PAHs lack TEF-values and they are commonly not included in risk assessments. However, it is well known that they can act as potent co-carcinogens and, e.g. inhibit repair of DNA-damage induced by genotoxic PAHs. An additional factor is that other highly carcinogenic PAHs are often not included in risk assessments. For example, the genotoxic persistent biotransformation products of PAHs, oxy-PAHs, appear in significant amounts but lack TEF values (Lundstedt et al. 2006). Yet another factor is that PAH-contaminated soils probably contain the highly carcinogenic *dibenzo[*a*]pyrene* (DBP). DBP might be approximately 200 times more carcinogenic than B(a)P and might act as a transplacental carcinogen (Yu et al. 2006).

Mechanistic studies support the fact that a mixture of PAH induces 5–10 times more tumours than the equivalent amount of B(a)P. Thus, the genotoxicity of B(a)P has been shown to be increased in mixture (Tarantini et al. 2009). Furthermore, when the TEF-approach was applied for effects of soil extracts on DNA-damage signalling it was found that TEQ values did not correlate with the effect on the DNA-damage signalling proteins (Mattsson et al. 2009). Together, these data indicate interactions between PAHs and suggest that existing TEF-values do not predict effects induced on DNA-damage signalling. Furthermore, the data show that complex PAH mixtures, and oxy-PAHs that have never been tested in animal experiments, may elicit unpredictable signalling responses with high potency. This is in line with data showing that polar and non-polar extracts from human breast milk modulate the genotoxicity of B(a)P in an unpredictable manner (Kalantzi et al. 2004). Together, these data indicate that the available TEF-scales are not sufficient for predicting the risk of complex PAH mixtures. They also underline the need to understand how PAHs interact among PAHs

and with other chemicals. Thus, other environmental pollutants such as arsenic, dioxins and PCBs have been shown to interact with PAH-induced DNA-damage signalling (Huang et al. 2008; Al-Anati et al. 2009; Al-Anati et al. 2010). These studies show that arsenic and PCBs might functionally disable tumour suppressor p53 and thus increase the genotoxicity of PAHs.

6.4 Research and development needs

A recent report lists several factors that indicate that environmental cancer risks have been seriously underestimated so far. The report also shows that some cancer incidences are increasing without reasonable explanations (President's Cancer Panel 2009). One factor of importance might be interacting effects of carcinogens. Generally there is a lack of knowledge about how carcinogens interact and how much these interactions contribute to carcinogenesis. This lack of knowledge includes interactions related to hormonal effects of carcinogens. Some important research topics are:

- Identify carcinogenic interactions in published literature.
- Characterize important “modes of interactions” for carcinogens, including interactions with hormones.
- Identify PAHs in common mixtures, e.g. urban air, which induce synergistic DNA damage and which may interact with, e.g. inflammatory effects caused by particles.
- Investigate how TEF-values for PAHs should be modified in an effort to include these interactions in risk assessment.
- Characterize how PAHs interact with other environmental contaminants, such as PCBs, dioxins and metals.

7 LUNG DISEASES

7.1 General background

Allergic asthma manifestations of disease and asthma symptoms can be related to occupational exposure to allergens and the presence of specific Immunoglobulin E (IgE) antibodies. Depending on the studied age group, 10–80% of persons diagnosed with asthma have IgE levels indicative of sensitization. Environmental factors have a high impact on allergic sensitization, as has the amount of allergen to which a person is exposed. This has been demonstrated most convincingly in occupational allergy, where up to 50% of the exposed subjects have been sensitized to the exposed allergen. Subjects with atopic disposition are usually sensitized at a lower exposure than non-atopic subjects.

Asthma which is unrelated to allergic sensitization is caused by agents that do not induce the production of IgE antibodies, i.e. non-allergic asthma. Airway infections (often viral), exercise, cold air, tobacco smoke, irritating agents such as perfumes, welding smoke and exhausts are some of the most common factors that induce asthma symptoms through non-allergic mechanisms. The use of certain drugs, such as anti-hypertensive drugs (beta blockers) and anti-inflammatory drugs (COX inhibitors), may also lead to an increase of symptoms in asthma. In contrast to allergic asthma, the prevalence of non-allergic asthma increases with age.

Figure 7.1 Spirometry is a common test to measure lung function.

As early as in 1950, Fletcher et al (Fletcher 1958) reported a higher prevalence of chronic bronchitis symptoms and emphysema especially in miners. This might be explained by inflammation in the airways caused by deposited particles. The inflammation causes a decrease in lung function (FEV_1) and leads, in the long run, to chronic airway obstruction. In a study, where 5,724 persons with mild chronic obstructive pulmonary disease (COPD) were followed yearly with spirometry, bronchial methacholine provocation and questionnaires regarding occupational exposure for five years, it was found that every year of occupational exposure caused an additional FEV_1 decrease of 10 ml (Harber et al. 2007).

Apart from exposure to tobacco smoke, occupational exposure to gases, dust and smoke is of importance for the development of COPD. This type of exposure is common in the plastic-, rubber- and textile industries. Globally, the most important risk factor for the development of COPD is indoor air pollutants, such as biomass fuels used to heat and cook in poorly ventilated homes. The WHO estimates that, in countries of low and middle income, 36% of people develop COPD due to exposure to indoor smoke from biomass fuels (Mannino and Buist 2007).

The prevalence of chronic and occupationally related airway symptoms is higher in farmers than in the general population. A prevalence between 6-32% of chronic bronchitis and COPD have been reported in farmers, with the highest prevalence in smoking farmers and swine farmers (Eduard et al. 2009). High exposure levels of organic dust, particles and gases such as ammonia and hydrogen sulphide contribute to the harmful environment associated with swine breeding. Healthy, previously non-exposed volunteers get an acute airway inflammation with influenza-like symptoms and increased bronchial responsiveness to methacholine when

exposed in swine confinement buildings, a condition called organic dust toxic syndrome (ODTS). In connection with the exposure there is a huge immigration of inflammatory cells from the blood into the airways and a release of pro-inflammatory mediators (cytokines) to both the upper and lower airways as well as the circulatory system. A few hours of exposure induce airway neutrophilia with up to a 100-fold increase of neutrophils in bronchial alveolar lavage (BAL) fluid and 3–4-fold increase in lymphocytes and alveolar macrophages.

7.2 Discussion

7.2.1 Different asthma phenotypes

Occupational asthma results from workplace exposure to dust or chemicals and is one of the most common occupational diseases in the EU. Cigarette smoking is an important factor associated with poor symptom control and treatment resistance in patients with asthma, and patients with asthma who quit smoking showed less airway obstruction, suggesting that smoking cessation is crucial in the management of asthma (Chalmers et al. 2002).

Moffatt et al. who, in a recent study, examined whether genetic risk factors are useful in identifying subtypes of asthma found that asthma is genetically heterogeneous and that elevation of serum IgE levels has minor role in asthma patho-physiology (Moffatt et al.). However, below we will describe three different asthma types developed from combined exposure to different stressors and the difficulty faced in preventing and treating individuals with asthma.

An important cause of exposure to high molecular agents is in work with laboratory animals. Between 10-23%, depending on the definition of laboratory animal allergy, of the personnel working with laboratory animals, in particular rats and mice, develop laboratory animal allergy (Elliott et al. 2005). Exposure in laboratory animal facilities not only involves laboratory allergens but also exposure to non-allergic microbial agents, e.g. endotoxin. Endotoxin (lipopolysaccharide (LPS)) is known as a pro-inflammatory stimulus and exposure to endotoxin in farmers has been correlated with decrease in lung function. Symptoms like rhinitis, conjunctivitis and/or urticaria arise mostly during the first years of animal work, and nearly half of the persons with symptoms also have asthma (Renström et al. 1994). The risk of developing laboratory animal allergy in a laboratory with low exposure levels was investigated in a cross-sectional study consisting of 80 laboratory animal workers. Risk factors for laboratory animal allergy were: presence of atopy with positive Phadiatop® and/or increased levels of total IgE, allergy to other furred animals and working with male rats or female mice (Renström et al. 1995). Prevention studies aiming to minimize the risk of sensitization, in which the personnel were educated to increase the usage of individual protective equipment and improve working and animal handling routines have been performed. However, non-occupational exposure to animals, particularly household pets, may confound the occupational exposure to animals because many animals used in the laboratory are also the same animals kept as pets.

Airway inflammation in connection with diisocyanate-induced asthma is similar to what is observed in other asthma phenotypes. Bronchial biopsies from patients with isocyanate asthma show increased numbers of eosinophilic granulocytes in the mucosa and submucosa and increased numbers of mast cells in the epithelium. In broncho-alveolar lavage and biopsies from the airway mucous membrane an increased occurrence of activated lymphocytes and eosinophilic granulocytes has been observed (Saetta et al. 1995). Approximately 10–20% of diisocyanate-reactive individuals have diisocyanate-specific

IgE antibodies. Dual and late asthmatic reaction induced by diisocyanates are usually more severe, last longer and are associated with transient increase of bronchial responsiveness to non-specific stimuli, such as methacholine, and are more resistant to therapy. Personal or family history of atopy, allergic disease and other possible risk factors, such as smoking, do not appear to be risk factors for the development of diisocyanate asthma.

Skiers, as well as other endurance athletes with asthma symptoms during heavy physical exertion, show a different morphological profile compared with “classic” asthma. The combination of exercise and environmental exposure may enlarge airway sensitivity. Two examples of athletes with a high prevalence of asthma symptoms and increased bronchial responsiveness are ice-hockey players exposed to exhaust from the ice-machines (Lumme et al. 2003) and swimmers exposed to chlorine in the swimming hall (Helenius et al. 1998).

These examples clearly demonstrate that asthma is not one homogenous disease with uniform morphological alterations, but asthma is rather a syndrome which can be developed from exposure to one or a combination of different stressors, consisting of several conditions with different clinical, morphological and inflammatory profiles.

7.2.2 Exposure to organic material

In healthy subjects, acute exposure in a pig barn causes an intense airway inflammation with a near 100-fold increase in neutrophils, a 3–4-fold increase in lymphocytes and increase in pro-inflammatory cytokines and enhanced bronchial responsiveness. Concentrations up to 28.5 mg/m³ of inhalable dust have been found in pig confinement buildings. The exposure of organic dust is a combined exposure of multiple microbial components, including bacterial endotoxin

(lipopolysaccharide, LPS) and peptidoglycans.

Farmers have a higher prevalence of airway symptoms and chronic bronchitis than the general population, and farmers run an increased risk of developing COPD. However, in swine farmers who have been working in this environment on a daily basis, the immune response to the pig barn environment is attenuated compared with the response observed in non-exposed healthy volunteers after an acute exposure (Palmberg et al. 2002). After acute exposure, farmers report fewer symptoms and attenuated physiological (lung function and bronchial responsiveness) and inflammatory (exhaled nitric oxide, cell numbers and cytokines in sputum and nasal lavage) alterations than healthy controls. These results show that farmers with chronic exposure develop some kind of immunological tolerance to organic dust (Sundblad et al. 2009). A “healthy worker effect” in farmers with chronic symptoms cannot be disregarded, but as farming is often an inherited profession this effect is likely to be minor.

The effect of wearing different types of masks to reduce the exposure to particles, gases and endotoxins has been studied (Sundblad et al. 2006). Using a mask with both a particle filter (to eliminate exposure to particles down to the size of viruses) and a gas filter during exposure in the pig barn markedly reduces the inflammatory response, but the effect on bronchial reactivity remains. Although when endotoxin exposure was reduced by 99% (measured with

nasal samplers) some biological effects remained, which indicates that endotoxin plays a minor role as a trigger factor. It has been suggested that the increase in bronchial responsiveness is caused by ultra-fine particles in the confinement building.

Smoking is the most common cause of COPD, but other factors contribute to the high prevalence of the disease. In subjects with α_1 -antitrypsin deficiency, active smoking severely increases the risk of COPD. In addition, occupational exposures and passive smoking enhance lung function decline and/or the prevalence of respiratory symptoms in subjects with α_1 -antitrypsin deficiency (Senn et al. 2005).

Smokers, like farmers, are continuously exposed to organic compounds which also include endotoxins. Clinical, physiological and inflammatory airway responses to acute pro-inflammatory agents (exposure in a pig barn) were attenuated in smokers compared with non-smoking controls (Sundblad et al. 2009), indicating that chronic exposure to tobacco smoke yields some kind of tolerance towards exposure to organic material in general.

Bronchial hyper-responsiveness describes an exaggerated airway-narrowing response to many environmental triggers and is characteristic of asthma. Bronchial hyper-responsiveness is measured by bronchial provocations using direct (methacholine) or indirect (exercise, dry air) stimuli. Methacholine challenge has a high sensitivity to identify bronchial hyper-responsiveness, and a negative test is often used to exclude asthma.

When bronchial responsiveness to methacholine was studied in 47 subjects, before and after exposure in a pig barn, a weak correlation between pre- and post-exposure bronchial responsiveness was found and bronchial responsiveness after exposure was almost identical in all subjects irrespective of the pre-exposure level. It was concluded that exposure to a strong pro-inflammatory stimulus, such as organic dust in a pig barn, enhanced bronchial responsiveness to methacholine up to a certain level irrespective of pre-exposure bronchial response. As approximately the same level was reached in all subjects the increase in bronchial responsiveness to methacholine following exposure in a pig barn represents what maximally can be achieved in healthy subjects (Strandberg et al. 2008).

7.3 Research and development needs

Between 5–10% of the population suffer from asthma and COPD. Asthma and chronic exposure to organic material within the farming environment are associated with chronic airway inflammation and airway symptoms but do not lead to COPD and emphysema. The inflammatory response in farmers and smokers leads to chronic bronchitis, but it is only smoking that is frequently associated with the disabling disease characterized by respiratory failure and premature death. Further studies to evaluate influences of regular occupational exposure on innate and adaptive immunity are therefore needed.

Research needs in this field are necessary to find the similarities and differences between the expression of disease and various types of exposure to determine “common pathways” for lung damage incurred following exposure to organic material in the following aspects:

- The consequence of combined exposure to occupational stressors and smoking to develop lung infirmity.
 - Development of COPD/emphysema.
 - Development of chronic bronchitis.

- The consequence of airway and lung exposure to occupational agents or combined exposure to develop systemic effects.
 - Different inflammatory markers.

8 ALLERGENS, IRRITANTS AND CONTACT DERMATITIS

8.1 General Background

The population is exposed to a multitude of chemical substances through skin contact with consumer products and exposure in the workplace. Many of these chemicals can cause skin effects or systemic toxicity. Skin sensitizers are widely distributed and may lead to chronic and disabling contact dermatitis. The symptoms are redness, itching, blisters and scaling on hands, face or other parts of the body. The economic burden of occupational skin disease is considerable, and is estimated to be more than €5 billion per year in Europe (Batzdorfer and Schwanitz 2004; English 2004; Blanciforti 2010).

Substances in chemical products, cosmetics and other type of products that come into skin contact may cause contact dermatitis due to irritation, sensitization, corrosion and burns or systemic toxicity. Skin contact with water, detergents and fresh food is, due to their irritative effects, among the most frequent causes of hand eczema. Hand eczema affects 10% of the adult population (1-year prevalence), women more often than men, younger people more often than older people, and is more frequent in certain occupations (Meding and Jarvholm 2002). Differences between genders, age groups and occupations are due to differences in exposure to sensitizers or irritants.

Contact allergy affects 15–20% of adults in the general population (Thyssen et al. 2009) children are also affected. The most prevalent causes are chemical substances in products and materials to which workers and consumers are exposed. Around 4,000 substances have been identified as skin sensitizers. The most frequent causes of contact allergy are metals (nickel, chromium and cobalt), fragrance chemicals, preservatives (such as chloromethyl/methyl isothiazolinones, benzisothiazolinone, formaldehyde releasers, methyldibromo glutaronitrile), plastic and rubber chemicals and hair dye substances. Contact allergy is a major cause of hand eczema. Another major cause of hand eczema is wet work, such as frequent or prolonged exposure to water, detergents, fresh food, organic solvents, and occlusive protective gloves.

Allergic contact dermatitis is the clinical disease caused by skin exposure to skin sensitizing substances (contact allergens). Contact allergens are low-molecular-weight substances (haptens) that may cause *induction* of contact allergy (*sensitization*). The hapten passes the skin barrier, is taken up by dendritic cells in the skin and is transported to draining lymph nodes. In the lymph node, the hapten is transformed to a complete allergen by addition to a protein which is presented to immuno-competent cells, T-lymphocytes. Re-exposure of a sensitized individual may result in *elicitation* of allergic contact dermatitis. Further exposure to the substance has to be minimized to avoid dermatitis. The dose sufficient for induction is generally larger than the dose for elicitation. Patch testing (epicutaneous testing) is the diagnostic procedure to detect contact allergy.

Combined exposure to skin sensitizers, skin irritants and skin penetration enhancers is very common in workers, consumers, and children. It is well known that allergic contact dermatitis is often aggravated by concomitant exposure to skin irritants. It is also known that an impaired skin barrier, as seen in irritant contact dermatitis, facilitates skin absorption, sensitization and allergic contact dermatitis. The effects of these factors on skin have, however, generally been studied one by one, not in combination.

Harmful effects by hazardous skin exposure can be prevented by exposure reduction. Legislation plays an important role in the prevention of contact dermatitis, particularly the EU

regulation on CLP, the EU Cosmetics Directive and national workplace regulations, which are largely based on hazard identification and risk assessments.

8.2 Discussion

8.2.1 Predictive testing for skin sensitizing potential or potency

Animal and human assays are used in hazard identification and risk assessment for regulatory purpose. The OECD guidelines for the animal test methods used in harmonized classification of substances, according to their potential to cause skin sensitization, are the guinea pig maximization test (GPMT), the Buehler test (OECD 1992, 1981), and the local lymph node assay (LLNA) in mice (OECD 2010, 2002). International recommendations for human assays are also described (Johansen et al. 2011).

Animal assays

There are certain benefits but also severe limitations regarding the guideline test methods in relation to combined exposure:

- The animal test methods are designed to study one chemical at a time and they are not designed for preparations, which dominate skin exposure in humans.
- The original guinea pig test methods are designed for one induction concentration only. Through statistical development, the original one-dose-guinea-pig test methods is transformed and used for dose-response studies of induction as well as elicitation (Andersen et al. 1985; Andersen and Maibach 1985).
- The LLNA includes exposure to at least three concentrations and one vehicle control, making it an assay for allergenic potency of the test chemicals (Kimber et al. 1989). As the LLNA assays induction, not elicitation, it cannot be used for cross-reactivity studies.
- The limited exposure time in animal assays does not reflect the extended and repeated exposure in the workplace or from consumer products.

Human assays

Predictive human sensitization tests involve attempts to induce a long-lasting or permanent immunologic sensitization in the individual. One such test is the human repeated insult patch test (HRIPT), which is promoted by industry. Predictive sensitization testing in humans, however, is considered unethical due to the risk that the procedure may induce lifelong skin sensitization, and also due to the risk of failure in predicting sensitizing potential. This has been stated by the ECHA Guidance for the implementation of REACH 2008, a WHO workshop outcome (van Loveren et al. 2008) and the EC Scientific Committees SCCNFP 2000, SCCP 2008 (Scientific Committee on Cosmetic Products and Non-food Products intended for Consumers (SCCNFP) 2000; Scientific Committee on Consumer Products (SCCP) 2008).

Diagnostic patch testing is the procedure used for the detection of contact allergy in humans, thus elicitation and not sensitization (Lindberg and Matura 2011). Patch testing is performed in dermatitis patients, in experimental and epidemiological studies, normally with single substances, standardized mixes containing related substances and with products (mixtures, at suitable concentration).

A range of tests, attempting to simulate normal exposure, are used for the elicitation of allergic contact dermatitis and they are useful in risk assessment (Johansen et al. 2011). The

method most frequently used is the repeated open application test (ROAT). Dose-response studies give information on elicitation potency, not induction.

8.2.2 Combined skin exposure to allergens, irritants and penetration enhancers

In working life and daily life, skin is normally exposed to skin sensitizers, skin irritants, and penetration enhancers that are deposited and accumulated on the skin from single or multiple sources. This may affect skin absorption, sensitization and elicitation.

How skin absorption is affected may be studied by *in vivo* techniques (microdialysis, tape stripping) and *in vitro* techniques.

The exposure dose needed for a sensitization is generally higher than the subsequent eliciting dose. There are no strict dose-response intervals for contact allergens. Several factors affect the sensitization risk: the inherent sensitizing potency of the substance; dose per area unit; duration and frequency of exposure; vehicle, occlusion, and temperature; and the condition of the skin – several of these factors represent combined exposures. Genetic predisposition plays a minor role.

Only few studies have systematically compared the effect of different vehicles on the outcome of LLNA with the same substance. The results show that different vehicles may result in broad variations (Basketter et al. 2003; Madsen et al. 2011). The outcome of predictive tests with the same substance may vary up to 20-fold, depending on the choice of vehicle in LLNA. This may then result in the misclassification of allergens, and is not considered to be properly addressed in the OECD guidelines.

The repeated, daily exposure to relatively mild skin irritants, such as detergents and water, may cause irritant contact dermatitis and impaired skin barrier, which then is less resistant to contact allergens. Exposure to more potent irritants, including alkali and some organic solvents, has a greater effect. Some substances enhance skin penetration of chemicals without causing skin irritation - examples are DMSO and dimethyl formamide. Occlusion contributes to enhanced skin penetration. Protective gloves are an important example, but also occlusion by certain vehicles. The dose needed for induction and elicitation of the contact allergy may also be reduced by simultaneous exposure to chemically related skin sensitizers.

Human elicitation test methods with different vehicles, pre-treatment of the skin with irritants etc, are used. Such methods may be used in broader attempts to study effects of combined exposures to chemicals. However, the procedures are not yet standardized.

8.2.3 Skin exposure assessment

Methods for quantification of skin exposure to most of the important sensitizing substances, skin irritants and penetration enhancers are lacking. The use of such methods is of ultimate importance when considering exposure to and effects by multiple exposures. During recent years, there has been increasing interest concerning skin exposure assessment. Sampling

Figure 8.1 Due to massive and combined exposure to skin irritants and sensitizers, hairdressing is a high-risk occupation for hand eczema.

methods have been developed, validated and used for the assessment of exposure to metals (acid wipe sampling, rinsing, tape stripping) (Liden et al. 2006), hair dyes (bag rinsing) (Lind et al. 2004), acrylates and epoxy (tape stripping), particles (suction sampler, dosimeter), wet work (observation) (Anveden et al. 2006) and pesticides (fluorescent tracer technique) (Aragon et al. 2006). Until now, dermatologists have generally discussed exposure in relation to the number of sensitized individuals, and skin exposure levels have not been assessed.

8.2.4 Cross-reactivity

Sensitized individuals, humans and animals, may react to substances that are chemically related to the sensitizer, although not previously exposed or sensitized to the substance. Such reactivity is called cross-reactivity. Groups of substances for which cross reactivity has been discussed are the metals nickel, chromium and cobalt, hair dye substances, and different isothiazolinone preservatives.

In risk assessment, risk management and diagnosis, it is important to know if simultaneous reactivity is due to cross-reactivity or multiple sensitization. It is, however, not possible to draw conclusions from patch testing in humans, due to their unknown previous exposure. Cross-reactivity can be assessed using the GPMT by challenge with several substances, but not by the LLNA, as the method considers only the induction phase. However, modified LLNA applications, including elicitation testing, may be used (Bonefeld et al. 2010).

8.3 Research and development needs

There is a great need to systematically study the effects caused by combined exposure to skin sensitizers, skin irritants, and skin penetration enhancers. Research should focus on areas where new knowledge may fill important knowledge gaps and contribute to a generic approach in risk assessment and risk management of skin sensitization, and to support diagnosis and prevention of contact dermatitis in workers, consumers and children. The following areas are considered to be of such key importance:

- Skin exposure assessment
 - Validated methods for the assessment of skin exposure to important skin sensitizers and skin irritants are needed.
 - Quantitative data on concomitant skin exposure to sensitizers and irritants is lacking.
- Combined skin exposure to allergens and penetration enhancers?
 - To what extent is sensitization influenced by simultaneous exposure to haptens and penetration enhancers?
- Vehicle effects on the outcome of induction and elicitation with skin sensitizers
 - The OECD guidelines for predictive testing in animals need further consideration.
 - Guidelines for dose-response elicitation testing in humans are needed.
 - How is skin absorption of contact allergens affected by exposure to irritants?
- Cross-reactivity vs multiple sensitization to clinically important skin sensitizers
 - For prevention, it is essential for prevention to know if the multiple reactivity recorded in some groups of skin sensitizers is due to cross-reactivity or to multiple sensitization

9 ENDOCRINE DISRUPTION

Endocrine disrupting compounds (EDCs) interfere with hormones and can cause several effects in animals and humans (WHO/IPCS 2002; Miljöhälsorapport 2005; Institutet för Miljömedicin (IMM) et al. 2006; Institutet för Miljömedicin (IMM) et al. 2007). Effects on sperm function, fertility, sex ratio, hypospadias, cryptorchidism, endometriosis, early puberty, breast cancer, endometrial cancer, testis cancer, prostate cancer, behavioural disorders and immune function, bone, and tooth abnormalities have all been linked to EDC exposure in humans and/or experimental models.

EDCs can act on different levels in the complex homeostasis of hormones. Inhibition or induction of specific enzymes involved in the biotransformation of hormones has been shown to affect levels of active forms of hormones as well as their elimination (see Chapter 4 for further information on mixture effects involving enzyme inducers/inhibitors). In addition, effects on synthesis, transport, genomic and non-genomic pathways of hormones have been reported. The most well-studied molecular targets are the nuclear receptor activation pathways. Since several compounds have been shown to act via the same or similar mechanisms- or modes of action, EDCs are often discussed concerning mixture effects.

Many studies of mixtures of EDCs have been published. However, whole mixture approaches seldom answer the question of whether the chemicals act in an additive, antagonistic or synergistic fashion. One of the major difficulties in assessing combined exposure to endocrine disruptors is the uncertainty about their potential to act together in an additive or synergistic manner. To address these concerns a recent report (Kortenkamp et al. 2009) has reviewed the studies available on endocrine disrupter mixtures in terms of additivity, antagonism or synergy.

9.1 Mixtures of oestrogenic chemicals

The female sex hormone oestrogen is involved in the development of different organ systems, not only the reproductive system - it is also important in males. Oestrogenic chemicals have been the focus of most of the work on endocrine disruptors. While the earlier efforts have mainly employed binary mixtures (reviewed in (Kortenkamp and Altenburger 1998) later work has also analyzed multi-component mixtures. "Oestrogenicity" is usually defined as causing similar responses as the endogenous oestrogen 17 β -estradiol (E2), which is used as a positive control. Thus, "oestrogenicity" can mean anything from affinity to the oestrogen receptor (ER α or β) *in vitro* to responses of the uterus *in vivo* (such as the uterotrophic assay). Several groups of oestrogenic chemicals have been studied, such as pesticides (different forms of DDT, endosulfan, pentachlorophenol), phytoestrogens (genistein, coumestrol), industrial chemicals (alkylphenols, bisphenol A, phthalates), pollutants (PAH) and Persistent Organic Pollutants (POPs) (methoxychlor, dieldrin, β -HCH). Kortenkamp (Kortenkamp et al. 2009) concludes

that the available evidence shows that dose (concentration) addition proved to be a valid tool for the prediction and assessment of the combined effects of oestrogen mixtures. The independent action approach led to underestimations of the observed effects.

9.2 Mixtures of androgen receptor antagonists and other anti-androgens

Androgens are key regulators of male sexual differentiation during the pre- and postnatal development. Chemicals that counteract androgen action (e.g. by antagonizing the androgen receptor activation) at some stage in this period can lead to malformations of the reproductive tract, a common effect of suggested EDC compounds in experimental studies. Changes in the AGD, retained nipples and alterations in the weight of sexual organs and accessory glands are frequently studied endpoints. These effects can arise through the antagonism of androgens at the steroid receptor level or via suppression of testosterone synthesis or function at other levels. Thus, anti-androgens can be defined narrowly as androgen receptor antagonists, but a broader definition in terms of counteracting the effects of androgens in a functional sense. In mixture studies, androgen receptor antagonism, suppression of testosterone synthesis *in vivo* and demasculinisation in male offspring exposed *in utero* have been studied (Kortenkamp et al. 2009). Also for anti-androgens, several groups of chemicals have been studied as mixtures, such as pesticides (vinclozolin, procymidone, deltamethrin, methiocarb, linuron and prochloraz), drugs (flutamide, finasteride) and industrial chemicals (phthalates). Kortenkamp (Kortenkamp et al. 2009) concludes that, in general, mixtures of anti-androgens followed dose addition. This was true even for mixtures composed of anti-androgens that displayed various mechanisms of action. The independent action approach always led to less conservative results and/or results less in agreement with data.

9.3 Mixtures of thyroid hormone-disrupting chemicals

Compared with oestrogens and anti-androgens, thyroid-disrupting mode of actions have been less well studied, fewer chemicals have been identified as thyroid hormone system disruptors - and only a few mixture studies exist. Thyroid-disrupting chemicals can alter the structure and function of the thyroid gland, as well as the homeostasis of thyroid hormones by interfering with associated regulatory enzymes and binding proteins. Changes in the circulating levels of thyroid hormones are often observed and this may result in severe consequences for the developing brain. Kortenkamp (Kortenkamp et al. 2009) concludes that most of the studies of thyroid-disrupting effects have analyzed the effects of mixtures (mainly dioxins and PCBs) without recording responses induced by individual mixture components, and this complicates assessment of combination effects in terms of additivity, synergism or antagonism.

9.4 Mixtures of retinoid-system modulating chemicals

Compared with oestrogens and anti-androgens, retinoid-system disrupting mode of actions have been less well studied, fewer chemicals have been identified as retinoid system disruptors and only a few mixture studies exist (Ahlborg et al. 1987; Ahlborg et al. 1989; Waern et al. 1990; Haag-Gronlund et al. 1998; Fattore et al. 2000; Chu et al. 2001). Changes in tissue as well as circulating levels of multiple retinoid forms occur following exposure to multiple categories of chemicals, and severe consequences are expected if exposure occurs during early development (Nilsson and Hakansson 2002). Like many other hormones, retinoid-system modulating chemicals can alter the structure and function of virtually every organ system in the body, as well as the homeostasis of thyroid hormones, by interfering with associated regulatory enzymes and binding proteins.

9.5 Mixture studies with endocrine disrupters of the same class

Taken together, Kortenkamp (Kortenkamp et al. 2009) concludes that there is strong evidence that steroid and thyroid hormone (endocrine) disrupting chemicals of the same class produce combination effects in a dose-additive manner. Where deviations from expected additivity occurred the differences between anticipated and observed effects were small. The reported deviations from dose-addition are, however, interesting from a conceptual viewpoint.

9.6 Combination effects of different classes of endocrine disrupters

Comparatively little work has been carried out with mixtures of different classes of endocrine disrupters, such as oestrogenic agents combined with anti-oestrogenic chemicals, or endocrine disrupters combined with other toxicants (Kortenkamp et al. 2009). However, a well-known example of “effect modulation” is the inhibitory effect of AhR agonists, such as dioxins and dioxin-like PCBs, on the action of oestrogenic chemicals.

Other examples of mixtures are agonists and antagonists of oestrogen and/or androgen receptors. Even more complicated are mixtures of disrupters of two or more hormone systems or mixtures of EDC and compounds with other mechanisms/modes of action. Other examples are compounds affecting the thyroid hormone and/or retinoid systems via different mechanisms, such as on the receptor, enzyme or protein-binding levels.

It is also clear that many individual compounds as well as groups of chemicals are able to simultaneously interfere with multiple endocrine pathways. For example, dioxins, PCBs and PBDEs all modulate both the steroid, thyroid and retinoid systems (Olsson et al. 1998; van der Ven et al. 2008; van der Ven et al. 2008). Here, only compounds interfering with oestrogen, androgen or thyroid hormone and retinoid systems are described in the light of available data. However, there are many more hormones or otherwise signalling molecules acting via nuclear receptors or via other pathways that are potential targets for chemicals with EDC properties and of potential importance in the context of mixture effects.

9.7 Research and development needs

From the studies reviewed by Kortenkamp (Kortenkamp et al. 2009) it can roughly be concluded that compounds acting via the same mechanism of action (e.g. oestrogen receptor agonists, androgen receptor antagonists or thyroid hormone modulators) interact in a dose-additive manner. Simply adding the concentrations and assuming equal potency is probably a simplification, and assuming equal potency as the most potent compound in the group will be (very) conservative.

When studying mixture effects the composition (pattern) of the mixture is very critical and should be mimicking the real-life exposure situation in humans. Of course, it is also important that the total dose level is not too high (causing other toxicity) so that the results can be extrapolated to low-level exposure in human scenarios.

A third critical aspect is the difficulty in extrapolating conclusions regarding type and level of mixture effect from *in vitro* (cell, receptor protein) to *in vivo* situations. For example oestrogenic chemicals are chemically very different and can consequently have varying toxicokinetic properties that greatly influence the actual concentrations of the individual compounds at the target site, and thus the potency of the compound.

The anti-oestrogenic effects of AhR ligands (e.g. dioxins and dioxin-like PCBs) are relatively well-characterized and in accordance with the TEF-system described in Chapter 10. However,

oestrogenic effects of dioxins have also been reported in experimental systems with no/low endogenous levels of oestrogen. These studies show that dioxins cannot simply be regarded as anti-oestrogenic and the relevance for the observed oestrogenic effects has to be further elucidated, e.g. in males and immature females.

In order to study the effects of mixtures of EDCs in simple test systems as well as in human studies (biomonitoring, epidemiology), biomarkers of early effects have to be developed. The development of such biomarkers, however, heavily relies on mechanistic research, i.e. to understand the mechanisms and modes of action of various kinds of EDCs.

In order to develop this area further there are two ways forward that have to be approached in parallel. First, to develop tools to handle mixtures in risk assessment and risk management, dose-addition may be one such tool. Such tools may first be crude, but should be refined further when more scientific data are generated. Second, research on the various mechanisms and modes of action involved in endocrine disruption as well as their relevance for the health risks of combined exposures is highly necessary. There is no doubt an urgent need to develop risk assessment capacities to assess combined exposures to endocrine active substances (EFSA 2010).

Specific research and development needs:

- Investigate the combined effects of EDCs acting via the same mechanism of action. This includes further studies on single compounds.
- Investigate the combined effects of EDCs acting via different mechanisms of action, but causing effects on the same target organ or function.
- Investigate if synergism is a plausible scenario in relevant exposure scenarios.
- Investigate the relevance of oestrogenic effects of dioxin-like compounds, in relation to their well-known anti-oestrogenic effects.
- Investigate if dose-addition is a suitable default model for practical risk assessment of specific groups of EDCs and, if so, develop a model that considers differences in potency and kinetic properties for individual compounds, in a similar way as the TEF-model for dioxins.

10 TOXIC EQUIVALENCY FACTORS (TEF) FOR DIOXIN-LIKE COMPOUNDS

The critical health effects of dioxin-like compounds (polychlorinated dibenzo-*p*-dioxins (PCDDs), dibenzofurans (PCDFs) and biphenyls (PCBs)) are on foetal development of the reproductive, nervous and immune systems. Dioxins are also known to be tumour promoters as well as show endocrine disrupting properties (see Chapter 9 for further information). Humans are exposed to dioxins throughout life from low levels in food, especially fatty food of animal origin (fish, meat, eggs and dairy products) as well as breast milk. The calculated average intake in Sweden shows exposure for adults is near the Tolerable Daily Intake (TDI (European Commission and Scientific Committee on Food 2001)), with a percentage of the population exceeding the TDI. The dioxin-like compounds have a common mechanism of action, i.e. activation of the Ah receptor (see Chapter 5 for further information). The toxicity of the most toxic dioxin, TCDD, is relatively well characterized. However, there are hundreds of congeners of dioxins and dioxin-like PCBs, of which about 30 are of toxicological significance.

In humans, dioxins have been shown to increase the risk of cancer and TCDD is classified as a human carcinogen by the IARC (International Agency for Research on Cancer (IARC) 1997). Human studies have shown relationships between dioxin levels and several health effects, such as chloracne; decreased immune defence; altered hormone levels; diabetes; effects on bone, teeth, sperm count, and cardiovascular disease. Early development of the central nervous system (behavioural effects), reproductive system, and immune system is particularly sensitive to dioxins. Both experimental and human studies have shown that foetuses are the most sensitive group, although breast-fed infants are the most highly exposed group.

In order to assess the combined toxicity of the most toxicologically relevant dioxins and dioxin-like PCBs the Toxic Equivalency Factor (TEF) system has been developed. TCDD is relatively well characterized regarding its toxicity and the potencies of other congeners are compared with that of TCDD. The Toxic Equivalent (TEQ) of a sample is the sum of the concentrations of the individual congeners multiplied by their individual TEFs. The TEF-scheme is a useful tool for risk assessment and risk management and is extensively used in risk management, e.g. for EU limit values for food, Swedish guidance levels for contaminated soil, and estimation of intake via food. As the dioxin-like compounds share a common mechanism of action, i.e. the activation of the Ah receptor, the dose-addition method, adjusting for potency, is justified and has been validated in experimental mixture studies.

The first set of internationally harmonized TEFs was developed in 1988 for dioxins (NATO/CCMS 1988). In 1993, the WHO and IMM developed the first TEFs for dioxin-like PCBs based on a database developed by the IMM (Ahlborg et al. 1994; Ahlborg and Hanberg 1994). Since then, revisions of the TEF-scheme have been coordinated by the WHO and

expert meetings have been held in Stockholm (at the IMM) in 1997 and in Geneva in 2005 (van den Berg et al. 1998; van den Berg et al. 2006). Today there are TEF-values for 17 PCDD/Fs and 12 PCBs. The criteria for congeners to be included in the TEF-scheme are:

- Affinity to the Ah receptor.
- Dioxin-like effects.
- Structural similarity to TCDD.
- Persistent and bioaccumulating.

10.1 Research and development needs

The TEF-system for dioxins and dioxin-like PCBs has been used for more than 20 years and is a very useful tool in risk assessment and risk management of these compounds. The quality and quantity of the toxicological basis for each individual TEF-value varies greatly, but the confidence in the TEFs for the congeners of most relevance to human health risk is higher than for less relevant congeners. In addition, mixture studies of the most important congeners in ratios similar to those in food have shown results very close to dose addition (after applying TEFs). Together, these results show a quite solid base for the TEF-system as a tool for risk assessment of dioxin-like compounds. However, there are some limitations and uncertainties that have to be further investigated and developed.

As the safety margin for dioxins is very small or non-existent refinements in all parts of the risk assessment are necessary, as well as a reduction of exposures. As TCDD (which is the toxicologically best characterized congener) accounts for only about 10% of the total TEQ in food, the size of the TEFs for other dioxins/PCBs are critical for the precision in the quantification of exposure. Further, the TEF-system is used and/or referred to in various legislations regarding, for example, legally binding limit values. Thus, the TEF-system needs to be further refined. The individual TEF-values should be revised regularly when new data become available. From 1993 to 2006 the revisions of the TEF-system have been coordinated by the WHO, but there is no permanent obligation for it to handle this issue, and it has been handled on a case-by-case basis. The database on which the TEF-systems have been based was first developed by the IMM in 1993 and has been updated several times since then. It is of importance that this database is also updated for coming revisions. Also, the validation of the dose-additive model should be further evaluated by real-life mixtures and using exposures and effects of human relevance.

Assumes similarity between endpoints

The endpoints studied and compared in the TEF database vary. Ideally, the critical effects of dioxins should be the basis for the TEFs. However, developmental studies are rarely or never available as a basis for setting TEFs. A mixture study on early development, however, validates the TEF-scheme.

Assumes similarities between species

The current TEFs are entirely based on rodent studies, mainly in rats. The potencies of different congeners compared with TCDD (TEFs) are assumed to be equal for rats and humans. In 1997, TEF-schemes for birds and fish were also published and these were very similar to that of rodents, with the exception that fish were less sensitive to mono-*ortho* PCBs than birds and rodents. The rat to human variation in sensitivity to various congeners can, however, only be studied for a limited number of endpoints *in vitro*, e.g. enzyme induction in peripheral lymphocytes.

One limitation with the current TEF-system and the underlying database is the precision (or lack of precision) in the TEF-values for *poor agonists*, such as the mono-*ortho* PCBs (van den Berg et al. 2006). It is unclear if these congeners are real agonists or if there are very small amounts of potent contaminants that could account for the effects observed. This issue has to be further investigated as these low-potent compounds occur at high concentrations and thus may make significant contributions to the total TEQ of certain samples.

Inclusion of other AhR agonists in the TEF-scheme has been proposed and discussed (van den Berg et al. 2006). It was concluded that there are not sufficient data on levels in food and human tissues and/or toxicity data in relation to TCDD for including more compounds/groups, but this has to be regularly evaluated at future TEF-revisions. The groups of compounds proposed to be included in the TEF-scheme at the revision in 2005 were polychlorinated naphthalenes (PCN), polybrominated dibenzo-*p*-dioxins and furans (PBDD/F), mixed polychlorinated and polybrominated dibenzo-*p*-dioxins and furans (PXDD/F).

It is of highly important to develop easy and rapid screening tests for dioxin-like compounds. To do so more mechanistic research is needed to understand the mechanisms/modes of actions of AhR agonists, i.e. what happens after the activation of the AhR and leading to the most sensitive effects on the developing foetus/child (see Chapter 9 for further information). When biomarkers of early steps in this process could be identified useful tests could be developed to screen samples for effects of concern. In addition, the same biomarkers could be used for biomonitoring and human studies to further refine the animal-to-human extrapolation.

Specific research and development needs:

- Investigate the relevance and accuracy of the current TEFs for the critical effects of dioxins on foetal development.
- Study the relevance and accuracy of the current TEFs based on data from rats to humans.
- Evaluate other groups of dioxin-like compounds for inclusion in the TEF-scheme. As a basis for evaluation more research is needed on both exposure and toxicity of such compounds.
- Identify biomarkers of sensitive effects of dioxin-like compounds that can be used for developing screening tests as well as for studying effects in humans

11 CONTAMINATED SOIL

Risk assessment of contaminated sites is a real-life example of assessing exposure to multiple pollutants. The risk to human health posed by contaminated soil depends on the total direct and indirect exposure to soil and the toxic properties. The direct exposure routes include ingestion of soil, inhalation of soil particles, dust and fumes/gases, and dermal contact with soil, while the indirect exposure routes include ingestion of locally produced foods, including, e.g., vegetables, fruit, berries, mushrooms, fish, meat, eggs, dairy products and drinking water (contaminated well water or fresh water, Figure 11.1). A detailed soil exposure analysis should be stratified for age and gender. The acute as well as the chronic exposure (lifetime exposure) needs to be assessed.

Figure 11.1 The direct and indirect exposure routes of contaminants from soil included (yellow) and not included (blue) in the generic guidance values from the Swedish EPA (Naturvårdsverket 2009; Naturvårdsverket 2009).

Different models have been developed for contaminated soil exposure assessment. Most models are based on deterministic methods, but probabilistic methods are suitable to use when distributional data is available. The probabilistic approach takes into account the variability and the uncertainty in the exposure assessment. A report on “Exposure factors in risk assessment – an inventory of basic data” from the Swedish EPA programme on “Sustainable Remediation” was published in 2008 (Naturvårdsverket 2008). The report lists datasets for exposure factors, of which some can be used for probabilistic exposure assessment of contaminated soil. However, distributional data on exposure routes, such as consumption of home-grown vegetables and tap water, and time-use patterns is rather scarce.

In the deterministic approach, exposure factors are used. As mentioned in the chapter on exposure (Chapter 2), the US EPA has published two reports on exposure factors, one for adults and one for children (US EPA 1997; US EPA 2008), covering a large number of exposure factors, of which many are applicable for contaminated sites.

The Swedish EPA has developed a deterministic computation model for health-based guidance values for soil (Naturvårdsverket 2009). It includes six exposure routes: ingestion of

soil, dermal contact, inhalation of dust and fumes, ingestion of locally grown vegetables and consumption of drinking water (when applicable, Figure 11.1). Exposure is integrated over all routes. Fish consumption is included in the model but not included in the calculation of the guidance values for contaminated soil. The model does not consider consumption of locally produced foods of animal origin, such as dairy products, eggs and meat.

The IMM has recently assisted the Swedish EPA in revising the Swedish model for risk assessment of contaminated sites and revising the generic guidance values for contaminants in soil. In addition, the IMM participated in the development of supporting guidance documents in this area (Naturvårdsverket 2009; Naturvårdsverket 2009).

There are currently guidance values for single compounds (e.g. metals) and groups of contaminants (chlorophenols, chlorobenzenes, PCBs, dioxins, PAHs, aliphatic and aromatic compounds). The combined effects of these groups are assessed in different ways, some more advanced and some very simple. Dioxins (including dioxin-like PCBs) are assessed using the TEF-system (see Chapter 9 for further information) and PAHs are assessed taking into consideration both TEFs and human effects of PAH mixtures using epidemiological data (see Chapter 6 for further information). Various fractions of aromatic and aliphatic compounds are assessed in an additive manner assuming equal potency within the group.

During the process of revising the model and the generic guidance values several research and development needs were identified. For example, the model does not take into consideration the combined effects of different (groups of) contaminants. The guidance reports address this issue and recommend the assessment of any mixture effects. The guidance favours the use of a dose-additive model for assessing effects of combined exposures. It is also recommended that the total assessment of more than one genotoxic carcinogen at a contaminated site will not lead to a higher total risk than 1 in 100,000. The assessment of PAH is particularly complicated as these compounds have a wide variation in their chemical/physical and toxic properties and the total effect of the mixture is difficult to predict (see Chapter 6 for further information).

11. 1 Research and development needs

At most contaminated sites several contaminants are identified. Although many combinations of contaminants are possible similar patterns occur due to similarities in former industrial processes. Thus, typical mixtures of concern will be identified and prioritized based on the existing knowledge of which contaminants co-occur at contaminated sites and which of these contaminants may be assumed to share a common effect or mode of action.

In the Swedish EPA model for the establishment of guidance values for contaminated soil the effects of combined exposures are currently only considered within certain groups of contaminants (e.g. PAHs, dioxins, PCBs). Mixture effects within these groups of compounds

are handled in different ways, by dose-addition/TEFs for PAHs, dioxins and dioxin-like PCBs, or by dose-addition assuming equal toxic potency as the potentially most toxic compound in a group, such as the aliphatic compounds. Moreover, for carcinogenic PAH an uncertainty factor is used to compensate for possible synergistic effects. There are research studies that show that mixture effects may also occur for other combinations of contaminants occurring in soil, in an additive or synergistic manner.

The following research and development areas have been identified:

- Investigate which contaminants co-occur at typical (model) contaminated sites, such as sawmills, chlor-alkali industries and glasswork areas, and develop exposure scenarios for these.
- Compile and evaluate current knowledge of contaminants typically occurring at contaminated sites and assumed to share a common effect or mode of action.
- Risk assessment of combined exposures to contaminants co-occurring at contaminated sites. The following mixtures of high concern have so far been identified: carcinogens such as PAHs and arsenic, EDCs such as cadmium and dioxins/PCBs, and neurotoxic compounds such as lead, mercury and dioxins/PCBs.

12 ENGINEERED NANOMATERIALS

12.1 General background

Nanotechnology holds considerable promise in many different technological areas and industrial sectors, including electronics, cosmetics, medicine, optics, alternative energy and soil and water remediation. The industrial production and use of nanoparticles is expected to be the driving force for the emerging new materials industry of the 21st century. However, the potential impact of these new materials on human health and the environment is viewed with apprehension. Indeed, our understanding of the potential health and safety issues posed by nano-scale materials lags behind the rapid commercialization of nano-products (Maynard et al. 2006).

Engineered nanomaterials are commonly defined as materials of less than 100 nm in one or more dimensions. However, the definition of a “nanomaterial” is not straightforward and is currently being discussed by numerous national and international regulatory agencies. The Joint Research Centre (JRC) of the European Commission recently published a report on considerations on a definition of nanomaterial for regulatory purposes (Lövestam et al. 2010).

Nano-scale materials often display novel physico-chemical properties when compared to materials of a coarser structure of identical chemical composition. Importantly, nano-scale materials have a much larger specific surface area i.e. a larger area to mass ratio than coarser materials (Oberdorster et al. 2005). Because biological effects of materials are often dictated by reactions taking place at the surface of the material, one may expect nanomaterials to be much more reactive than the same mass of material of a larger size, i.e. micron-scale or bigger. Moreover, nanoparticles may cross biological barriers in the body, e.g. from the lung to systemic circulation, or from the systemic circulation across the blood-brain barrier into the central nervous system, and could therefore exert unexpected toxicities (Shvedova et al. 2010).

Nanotoxicological research has come under focus in recent years, and numerous national and international research projects are currently devoted to studies of the potential hazards of engineered nanomaterials for human health and the environment, including a number of projects funded by the European Commission. One such project, designated FP7-NANOMMUNE, is currently being coordinated by the IMM and deals with the hazardous effects of various classes of nanomaterials on the immune system, using cell culture and animal model systems. However, there are, at present, few human data addressing the potential health hazards posed by nanoparticles under realistic exposure scenarios. One recent study claimed to provide the first evidence of “nanomaterial-related disease” in humans, attributing unusual and progressive lung disease among seven Chinese workers, two of whom died, to nanoparticle exposures in a print plant where a polyacrylic ester paste containing nanoparticles was used (Song et al. 2009). However, exposure data were completely lacking; moreover, the workers were likely to have been exposed to a cocktail of chemicals and fumes, making it difficult to ascertain the cause of the respiratory disease in the affected workers (Kagan et al. 2010).

The evaluation of the safety of engineered nanomaterials is an important challenge for the near future. It is too early to predict biological or toxicological responses on the basis of the physico-chemical characteristics of the nanomaterial. Therefore, a case-by-case approach for hazard identification is still required, and it is difficult to establish a risk assessment framework.

12.2 Current research: focus on carbon-based nanomaterials

Excessive oxidative stress has been proposed as a common paradigm for the toxicities of engineered nanoparticles (Nel et al. 2006). While widely accepted, not all studies comply with this general notion, thus pointing to the need for careful scrutiny of this pervasive concept (Shvedova et al. 2010). Moreover, several studies from different laboratories have demonstrated that carbon nanotubes (CNTs) may trigger inflammation and fibrosis in rodents upon administration into the airways or following peritoneal injection. Whether or not CNTs may induce carcinogenic effects with development of mesothelioma is debated, and some studies have provided evidence for such effects whereas other studies do not support this notion. These discrepancies may, in part, be explained by the fact that different sources of CNTs were utilized in the different studies. Indeed, as Poland et al. (Poland et al. 2008) have reported, samples of CNTs with a high proportion of long fibres ($> 20 \mu\text{m}$) are more pathogenic and exert more “asbestos-like” effects whereas short CNTs do not elicit such effects. In the latter study, the nanotubes were introduced into the peritoneal cavity of mice. More recent studies from other investigators have demonstrated that inhaled CNTs reach the subpleural tissue in mice resulting in subpleural fibrosis when the nanomaterial is given at high doses (30 mg/m^3), but not when lower doses are used (1 mg/m^3) (Ryman-Rasmussen et al. 2009). However, the issue of whether CNTs cause mesothelioma could not be answered by this study. In addition, a very recent study has shown that single-walled CNTs may undergo enzymatic, myeloperoxidase-driven biodegradation in neutrophils (Kagan et al. 2010). Importantly, the biodegraded nanotubes did not generate an inflammatory response when aspirated into the lungs of mice. These findings suggest that controlled biodegradation of CNTs could mitigate the severity of the associated inflammatory responses in exposed individuals.

Recent studies have shown that the sequential exposure of mice to SWCNTs and bacteria (*Listeria monocytogenes*) enhances pulmonary inflammation and infectivity (Shvedova et al. 2008). This suggests that the accidental exposure to CNTs, for instance in workers, could lead to increased susceptibility to lung infection in exposed populations. Furthermore, studies of normal and ovalbumin-sensitized mice exposed to a MWCNT aerosol have revealed that CNTs potentiate airway fibrosis in murine allergic asthma (Ryman-Rasmussen et al. 2009). This indicates that individuals with pre-existing allergic inflammation may be particularly susceptible to airway fibrosis resulting from inhaled MWCNT. Overall, these studies point to the importance of studying susceptible populations and not only “normal” or healthy subjects.

When studying the toxicity of engineered nanomaterials, it is of paramount importance to conduct a comprehensive material characterization of the sample, bearing in mind not only the physico-chemical properties of the nanomaterial per se but also the occurrence of contaminants and other residual material. It is well-known that a carbon nanotube sample may contain residual material (amorphous carbon) as well as large amounts of transition metals. Previous studies have shown that the iron content of non-purified CNTs accounts for the induction of oxidative stress whereas purified, iron-stripped CNT samples do not elicit such effects (Kagan et al. 2006). Furthermore, the presence of residual surfactant arising from the synthesis may explain the cytotoxicity of gold nanoparticles, and coating of the gold nanoparticles with a polymer substantially reduces their toxicity (Alkilany et al. 2009). Importantly, nanoparticles may also acquire a “coating” of environmental toxicants and could act as carriers of such pollutants into the body, resulting in unexpected toxicities. Recent studies demonstrated that endotoxin-contamination of gold nanoparticles resulted in the activation of immune-competent dendritic cells (DCs), whereas purified nanoparticles had no effect on phenotypic maturation or cytokine production of the DCs (Vallhov et al. 2006). It has also been shown that PAHs can adsorb to engineered nanoparticles such as fullerenes. Furthermore, the addition of natural organic matter (humic acids) further increased the sorption of PAHs and reduced the freely dissolved PAH concentrations (Hu et al. 2008). The high PAH sorption coefficients to suspended fullerenes suggest that the release of fullerenes to the aquatic environment might affect PAH fate and exposures. More research is needed on the combination effects of engineered nanomaterials and other stressors.

Figure 12.1 Allotropes of carbon. From top left: diamond, fullerene (C60), graphite, C540, fullerene (C70), single-walled carbon nanotube.

12.3 Research needs: hazard and exposure

There is a lack of health effects data for humans exposed to engineered nanomaterials. However, human data for another source of nanoparticle exposure are available, notably for the nanoparticles contained in diesel exhaust particulate (DEP). Indeed, while nanotoxicology is often viewed as a “new” scientific discipline, it is obvious that this novel area of research is based on the historical foundation of particle and fibre toxicology (Oberdorster et al. 2005). Therefore, it will be important to take into account the epidemiological data that exists on the association between exposure to ambient particulate matter and cardiovascular morbidity and mortality. Similarly, we have learned from decades of research that certain man-made fibres, notably fibres that are both thin, long, and biopersistent, may induce pathological changes in exposed individuals, including fibrosis of the lung, and mesothelioma. In fact, the pathogenic fibre paradigm is one of the strongest structure-activity paradigms in toxicology, and recent studies suggest that this paradigm is also relevant to our understanding of the hazardous

effects of CNTs (Donaldson et al. 2010). Nevertheless, research in this field is still not conclusive. Furthermore, we still lack an understanding of which physico-chemical properties are driving the toxicity of other engineered nanomaterials, including materials that are commonly used in consumer products, such as nano-Ag and nanoparticles of ZnO or TiO₂.

Maynard et al. (Maynard et al. 2006) noted that “the enormous diversity of engineered nanomaterials with different sizes, shapes, compositions and coatings matches, and possibly exceeds, that of conventional chemicals”. These authors proposed that benchmarked and validated high-throughput screening (HTS) protocols are needed to screen for potential hazards of the vast numbers of engineered nanomaterials that are now being produced. In 2007, the US EPA launched a project, entitled ToxCast™, to predict the toxicity of chemicals using computational chemistry, HTS, and various toxicogenomic technologies. There are at present few, if any, examples of the application of HTS to the assessment of engineered nanomaterials (Feliu and Fadeel 2010). However, it may be important to consider such automated methodologies. HTS would not replace conventional toxicology, but such approaches could aid in the prioritization of nanomaterials for further testing, including animal testing. In addition, systems biology approaches, including transcriptomics, proteomics and metabolomics could also aid in the categorization of nanomaterials.

There is still a lack of measurements related to the exposure of engineered nanomaterials in occupational settings and in the environment, thus making risk assessment difficult (Savolainen et al. 2010). Perhaps the most demanding challenge for risk assessment is the need to develop an intelligent, tiered testing strategy to be able to reduce the amount of resources required for risk assessment without jeopardizing the safe use of these novel materials. It is also evident that there are major regulatory challenges with respect to engineered nanomaterials. For instance, while the REACH legislation is suggested to cover all chemicals, including nano-scale materials, it remains to be understood how to implement REACH (Gwinn and Tran 2010). Are nanomaterials “new” materials? If so, should they be subject to specific regulation? For comparison, the US EPA issued a Federal Register notice in 2008 regarding CNTs to emphasize that single-walled CNTs are “new” materials i.e. chemical substances distinct from graphite or other allotropes of carbon. This ruling has implications for manufacturers and importers who wish to produce or import CNTs for commercial purposes. Clearly, more nanotoxicological research is needed to support adequate risk assessment.

12.4 Research and development needs

We are currently facing several important challenges which need to be met in order to enable a sustainable development of the nanotechnologies. Among the most urgent research needs are the following:

- Standardize and validate test methods for hazard assessment of individual nanoparticles as well as more complex nano-composite systems that are currently being developed.
- Develop high-throughput screening (HTS) platforms to enable the assessment of large numbers of nanomaterials and establish structure-activity relationships for classes of nanomaterials based on a detailed understanding of the physico-chemical properties of nanomaterials.
- Exposure studies, including human, i.e. occupational and consumer exposure as well as environmental exposure, focusing not only on exposure to individual nanomaterials but also the combined exposure to engineered nanomaterials and other chemical or biological stressors.

- Develop an intelligent, tiered testing strategy to be able to reduce the amount of resources for nanomaterial risk assessment without jeopardizing the safe use of these novel materials.

13 CONCLUSIONS: RESEARCH AND DEVELOPMENT NEEDS

Risk assessment of combined exposure is a complex task and the current situation faces major challenges. For many chemicals their potential health effects are unknown, and even less is known for combined exposures. Given that all people are in fact exposed to multiple chemicals by multiple routes in their daily life, this is a timely issue that needs more attention and further actions.

13.1 General research needs

An important area is the understanding of how single/multiple chemicals absorbed by the body behave at molecular-, cellular-, organ- and systemic level. This is obviously a very complex issue, since the normal cellular processes are far from being completely characterized.

Current methods for predicting toxicity of mixtures require knowledge about individual chemicals' mechanisms or modes of action. This is further complicated by the fact that chemicals may have different modes of action depending on organ or cell type, and depending on actual exposure levels, timing of exposures, as well as on lifestage. Furthermore, for accurate prediction, the identity of all the components in the mixture/combined exposure needs to be known, in addition to their concentrations and dose ratio.

One question of particular concern is if a combined exposure may cause synergism. What are the mechanisms underlying synergism and can such effects be predicted? This issue is discussed for groups of chemicals such as endocrine disrupting chemicals, carcinogens, nanomaterials and chemicals/stressors causing asthma/COPD or dermatitis.

Another factor that is of importance in the context of mechanisms is the sequential exposure over time, e.g. childhood exposures that affect or will be affected by a subsequent exposure later in life. What are the potential health effects by exposures at different time points in life? Potential gender differences in susceptibility are other factors that need attention (e.g. exposures to carcinogens and interaction with endocrine disrupting chemicals).

One special situation of combined exposures that calls upon attention is the simultaneous exposure to both toxic and beneficial agents in foods. One example is fish which contain both toxic substances such as POPs and methylmercury and at the same time is an important source of health beneficial long-chain n-3 polyunsaturated fatty acids and vitamins; another example is fibre-rich food which is considered healthy because of the content of fibres and antioxidants, but at the same time contains cadmium, which is associated with adverse effects on the kidneys and bones as well as endocrine disruption and cancer. Methods for evaluating the modifying effects of combined exposures to toxic and beneficial agents need to be developed and, so far, there are only a few studies dealing with integrated risk-benefit evaluation.

Considering all the chemicals/stressors in our environment and the numerous combinations these can generate, it is not possible to test them all. Priority mixtures and relevant combined exposures should therefore be identified. Relevant endpoints should be recognized and studied.

A relevant question in the area of combined or mixed exposure is low-dose exposure. Some studies have reported that low-dose exposures in combination can cause significant biological

or health effects, which were not observed at single exposures. Whether these results are due to additive or synergistic actions need to be thoroughly evaluated.

In this report several research needs have been identified to meet the problems with combined exposures. These research needs reflect the different areas of research and risk assessment within the IMM and include, e.g. toxicokinetic modelling, epidemiological methodology that take into account combined exposures, improved exposure information, further evaluation and development of the TEF-system, methods for assessing skin exposure, research on chemicals' mechanisms of action and endocrine disruption. Other areas of importance are lung diseases caused by combined exposures and potential effects caused by nanomaterial in combination with other substances. In addition, models for predicting toxicity could be improved and developed. Techniques/areas that should be further developed are, e.g. epigenetic approaches and the development of improved biomarkers for effects.

13.2 Specific research needs

13.2.1 Exposure

A major challenge in exposure assessment is to determine the total exposure, via all relevant routes and pathways, in various groups of the population and for relevant time frames, and at the same time considering the timing and the sequence of exposure. There is a general lack of information regarding exposure, and in particular for combined exposures. Development of validated deterministic and probabilistic exposure models, for long-term and short-term exposure, and for various types of exposure scenarios, is needed. Specific actions to help fill some of the data gaps are outlined below:

- Develop harmonized methods for human exposure assessment (including biomonitoring).
- Create an inventory and gather representative exposure data and exposure factors/life-style factors suitable for modelling.
- Group chemicals based on common endpoint or effect, and that are typically present together in the environment.
- Develop and validate typical human exposure scenarios and exposure models for combined exposures.
- Develop models for retrospective occupational exposures.
- Link occupational exposure with toxicological research.
- Validate models for occupational exposure based on expert judgment.
- Construct and develop national exposure databases for environmental and occupational exposures.

13.2.2 Biomarkers

Biological exposure monitoring can be used to identify combined exposures to chemicals that may potentially cause harm to human health. Effect biomarkers could be further developed to assess the effect of combined exposures. The following research and development needs have been identified:

- Develop and validate *exposure* biomarkers suitable to detect combined exposures.
- Develop and validate *effect* biomarkers for combined exposures, e.g. for carcinogens and endocrine disrupting chemicals.

13.2.3 Toxicokinetics

Toxicokinetics is important in assessing combined exposures as the toxic effect is directly related to the target dose at specific targets in the body, but exposure is often assessed/measured as the external dose. Thus, a change in the toxicokinetics because of combined exposure may also affect the dose-response and dose-effect relationships and, hence, toxicity. The following research and development needs have been identified:

- Literature survey of interaction effects of combined exposures on ADME processes.
- Systematic study of metabolic interactions of low-dose chemical mixtures *in vitro* and *in silico*.
- To determine the reactive intermediate burden caused by chemical mixtures *in vitro* and *in silico*, as a proxy for target dose.
- PBPK modelling of combined exposures, using *in vitro* and *in silico* metabolic data.
- Integrate PBPK approaches, including, e.g. *in vitro* and *in silico* data on interaction, Monte Carlo simulations to address exposure and intraspecies variability and the median effect principle and response surface methodologies to detect and quantify additivity, synergism and antagonism.

13.2.4 The aryl hydrocarbon receptor (AhR) and cytochrome P4501A1

CYP1A1 is one of the best characterized xenobiotic-metabolizing enzymes. It is also the most important enzyme for the catabolic breakdown of endogenous AhR ligands. Different compounds can lead to either depletion or excess of the endogenous AhR ligand, depending on if they induce or inhibit the CYP1A1 enzyme. Therefore, the combined effect of different types of substances in mixtures that interfere with the AhR and/or the CYP1 enzymes via different mechanisms may be under-estimated if the risk assessment is restricted to dose addition. The following research and development needs have been identified:

- Perform mechanistic research to identify AhR-related processes of relevance for interactions.
- Investigate how single chemicals and mixtures can interfere with CYP1A1 mechanisms.

13.2.5 Cancer

Development of tumours takes many years and it is generally accepted that it is a multistep process. It is well established that chemicals can speed up the carcinogenic development. Chemicals can be both “initiators” and “promoters” or facilitate progression, a scenario which opens up numerous interactions between xenobiotics. The following research and development needs have been identified:

- Identify carcinogenic interactions in published literature.
- Characterize important “modes of interactions” for carcinogens, including interactions with hormones.
- Identify PAHs in common mixtures in, e.g. urban air, which induce synergistic DNA damage and which may interact with, e.g. inflammatory effects caused by particles.
- Investigate how TEF-values for PAHs should be modified in an effort to include these interactions in risk assessment.
- Characterize how PAHs interact with other environmental contaminants, such as PCBs, dioxins and metals.

13.2.6 Lung diseases

Allergic asthma indicators of disease and asthma symptoms can be related to occupational exposure to allergens and the presence of specific IgE antibodies. Environmental factors have a high impact on allergic sensitization, as has the amount of allergen to which a person is exposed. High prevalence of chronic bronchitis and COPD may be explained by inflammation in the airways caused by occupational exposure to gases, dust and tobacco smoke. The following research and development needs have been identified:

- Develop inflammatory biomarkers for combined exposure to occupational stressors.
- Find similarities and differences between the expression of disease and various types of exposure to determine “common pathways” for lung damage acquired following exposure to organic material in the following aspects:
 - Combined exposure of occupational stressors and smoking to develop COPD/emphysema and chronic bronchitis.
 - Combined exposure of occupational stressors to develop systemic effects.
- Evaluate influences of combined occupational exposure on innate and adaptive immunity.

13.2.7 Allergens, irritants and contact dermatitis

The population is exposed to a multitude of chemical substances through skin contact with consumer products and exposure in the workplace. Many of these chemicals may cause skin effects or systemic toxicity. Skin sensitizers are widely distributed and may lead to chronic and disabling contact dermatitis. The following research and development needs have been identified:

- Validate methods for assessment of skin exposure to important skin sensitizers and skin irritants.
- Acquire quantitative data on concomitant skin exposure to sensitizers and irritants.
- Study sensitization influenced by simultaneous exposure to allergens (e.g. haptens) and penetration enhancers.
- Study vehicle effects on the outcome of induction and elicitation with skin sensitizers.
- Study how skin absorption of contact allergens is affected by exposure to irritants.
- Study cross-reactivity vs. multiple sensitizations to clinically important skin sensitizers.
- Develop guidelines for dose-response elicitation testing in humans.

13.2.8 Endocrine disruption

Endocrine disrupting compounds (EDCs) have been shown to be able to interfere with hormones, such as oestrogen, androgen, thyroid hormone and retinoids. Many studies of mixtures of EDCs have been published and a dose-addition approach has been suggested for compounds acting via the same mechanism of action, e.g. as oestrogen receptor agonists. However, there are large knowledge gaps and uncertainties regarding both individual endocrine disrupters and mixtures thereof. The following research and development needs have been identified:

- Investigate the combined effects of EDCs acting via the same mechanism of action. This includes further studies on single compounds.
- Investigate the combined effects of EDCs acting via different mechanisms of action, but causing effects on the same target organ or function.
- Investigate if synergism is a plausible scenario in relevant exposure scenarios.
- Investigate the relevance of oestrogenic effects of dioxin-like compounds, in relation to their well-known anti-oestrogenic effects.

- Investigate if dose-addition is a suitable default model for practical risk assessment of specific groups of EDCs and, if so, develop a model that considers differences in potency and kinetic properties for individual compounds, in a similar way as the TEF-model for dioxins.

13.2.9 Toxic equivalency factors (TEF) for dioxin-like compounds

The WHO system for toxic equivalency TEF has been used for many years to assess the combined effects of dioxin-like compounds. But due to the small or absent margin of safety the TEF-model needs further development and refinement in order to reduce the uncertainties within the model. The following research and development needs have been identified:

- Investigate the relevance and accuracy of the current TEFs for the critical effects of dioxins on foetal development.
- Study the relevance and accuracy of the current TEFs based on data from rats to humans.
- Evaluate other groups of dioxin-like compounds for inclusion in the TEF-scheme. As a basis for evaluation more research is needed on both exposure and toxicity of such compounds.
- Identify biomarkers of sensitive effects of dioxin-like compounds that can be used for developing screening tests as well as for studying effects in humans.

13.2.10 Contaminated soil

At most contaminated sites several contaminants are identified. Although many combinations of contaminants are possible similar patterns occur due to similarities in former industrial processes. Thus, typical mixtures of concern have to be identified and prioritized based on existing knowledge on which contaminants that co-occur at contaminated sites and which of these contaminants may be assumed to share a common effect or mode of action.

In the Swedish EPA model for the establishment of guidance values for contaminated soil the effects of combined exposures are currently only considered for certain groups of contaminants (e.g. PAHs, dioxins, PCBs). Mixture effects within these groups of compounds are handled in different ways, by dose-addition/TEFs for PAHs, dioxins and dioxin-like PCBs, or by dose-addition assuming equal toxic potency as the potentially most toxic compound in a group, such as the aliphatic compounds. Moreover, for carcinogenic PAHs an uncertainty factor is used to compensate for possible synergistic effects. There are research studies that show that mixture effects can also occur for other groups of contaminants in soil, in an additive or a synergistic manner. The following research and development areas have been identified:

- Investigate which contaminants that co-occur at typical (model) contaminated sites, such as sawmills, chlor-alkali industries and glasswork areas, and develop exposure scenarios for these.
- Compile and evaluate the current knowledge of contaminants typically occurring at contaminated sites and assumed to share a common effect or mode of action.
- Risk assessment of combined exposures to contaminants co-occurring at contaminated sites. The following mixtures of high concern have so far been identified: carcinogens such as PAHs and arsenic, endocrine disrupting compounds such as cadmium and dioxins/PCBs, and neurotoxic compounds such as lead, mercury and dioxins/PCBs.

13.2.11 Engineered nanomaterials

The evaluation of the safety of engineered nanomaterial is an important challenge for the near future. It is too early to predict biological or toxicological responses on the basis of the

physico-chemical characteristics of the nanomaterial. In general, more research is needed on both single and the combined exposure of engineered nanomaterial. The following research and development needs have been identified:

- Standardize and validate test methods for hazard assessment of complex nano-composite systems.
- Exposure studies, including human, i.e. occupational and consumer exposure as well as environmental exposure, focusing on the combined exposure to engineered nanomaterials and other chemical or biological stressors.
- Investigate potential interactions between engineered nanomaterials and known toxic chemicals.

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Glossary

Additivity	When the “effect” of the combination is estimated by the sum of the exposure levels or the effects of the individual chemicals (US EPA 2000).
Aggregate exposure	The demographic, spatial and temporal characteristics of exposure to a single chemical through all relevant pathways and routes (WHO 2009).
Antagonism	When the effect of the combination is less than that suggested by the component toxic effects. Antagonism must be defined in the context of the definition of “no interaction”, which is usually dose or response addition (US EPA 2000).
Biomarker	A biomarker is any substance, structure or process that can be measured in the body or its products and influence or predict the incidence of outcome or disease. Biomarkers can be classified into markers of exposure, effect and susceptibility (IPCS, WHO, 2001).
Concentration addition	See dose additivity.
Cumulative risk	The combined risks from aggregate exposures to multiple agents or stressors (US EPA 2007).
Cumulative risk assessment	An analysis, characterization and possible quantification of the combined risks to health or the environment from multiple agents or stressors (US EPA 2007).
Combined exposure	Defined here as the exposure to multiple chemicals by single or multiple routes.
Dose additivity	When each chemical behaves as a concentration or dilution of every other chemical in the mixture. The response of the combination is the response expected from the equivalent dose of an index chemical. The equivalent dose is the sum of component doses scaled by their toxic potency relative to the index chemical (US EPA 2000).
Hazard Index	Method based on dose addition. The sum of hazard quotients for all chemicals to which an individual is exposed. A hazard index value of 1.0 or < 1.0 indicates that no adverse human health effects are expected to occur (US EPA 2000).
Independence	See response addition.
Interaction	Occurs when two or more chemicals interact and the effects are either more than additive (synergism) or less than additive (antagonism) (US EPA 2000).
Mixture	Defined here as the combination of two or more chemicals with which organisms come in contact, either simultaneously or sequentially.
Mechanism of action	Contrast to mode of action by an understanding of the molecular basis for an effect, see further Mode of

	action.
Mode of action	Describes the key events and processes starting from the point of toxicant-cell interaction and leading to the onset of a health endpoint (US EPA 2000).
No observed effect level	The highest exposure level at which there are no biologically significant increases in the frequency or severity of adverse effect between the exposed population and its appropriate control (Glossary, US EPA)
Physiologically Based Pharmacokinetic (PBPK) Model	Mathematical modeling of the pharmacokinetic (or toxicokinetic) behavior of a substance, based on measured physiological parameters (adapted from (Nordberg M et al. 2004)).
Response addition	When the toxic response from the combination is equal to the conditional sum of component responses as defined by the formula for the sum of independent event probabilities. For two chemical mixtures, the body's response to the first chemical is the same whether or not the second chemical is present (US EPA 2000).
Relative Potency	The ratio of the potency of a compound to the standard toxicant in that specific study; a concept similar to toxic equivalence but based on a single study, species, or matrix, etc., and not integrated with other Relative Potencies to obtain a general TEF (US EPA 2000).
Stressor	A stressor is any physical, chemical or biological entity that can induce an adverse response (US EPA 2007).
Synergism	When the effect of the combination is greater than that suggested by the component toxic effects. Synergism must be defined in the context of the definition of "no interaction", which is usually dose or response addition (US EPA 2000).
Toxic Equivalency Factors	TEFs are consensus estimates of a compound-specific toxicity/potency relative to the toxicity/potency of an index chemical. TEFs are the result of expert scientific judgment using all of the available data and taking into account uncertainties in the available data (US EPA 2000).

Abbreviations

ADME	Absorption, Distribution, Metabolism, and Excretion
AGD	Anogenital Distance
AhR	Aryl Hydrocarbon Receptor
BAL	Bronchial Alveolar Lavage
B(a)P	Benzo(a)pyrene
CER	Cancer-Environment Register
CLP	Classification, Labelling and Packaging
CNT	Carbon Nanotubes
COPD	Chronic Obstructive Pulmonary Disease
COX	Cyclooxygenase
CYP	Cytochrome P450
CYP1A1	Cytochrome P450 1A1
DBP	Dibenzo[al]pyrene
DC	Dendritic cells
DDT	Dichlorodiphenyltrichloroethane
DEET	N,N-diethyl-meta-toluamide
DEP	Diesel Exhaust Particles
DMSO	Dimethyl Sulfoxide
DMT1	Divalent Metal Transporter
ECHA	European Chemicals Agency
ED50	Effective Dose (in 50% of test population)
EDC	Endocrine Disrupting Compounds
EFSA	European Food Safety Authority
EPA	Environmental Protection Agency
ER	Oestrogen Receptor
EU	European Union
FICZ	6-formylindolo[3,2- <i>b</i>]carbazole
FEV1	Forced Expiratory Volume
FINJEM	Finnish job-exposure matrix
GPMT	Guinea Pig Maximization Test
HCB	Hexachlorobutadiene
HCH	Hexachlorocyclohexane
HAA	Heterocyclic Aromatic Amines
HI	Hazard Index
HPRT	Hypoxanthine-guanine PhosphoRibosyl Transferase
HRIPT	Human Repeated Insult Patch Test
HTS	High-throughput screening
IARC	International Agency for Research on Cancer
IgE	Immunoglobulin E
IMM	The Institute of Environmental Medicine, Institutet för Miljömedicin
IPCS	International Programme on Chemical Safety
JEM	Job Exposure Matrix
JRC	The Joint Research Centre
LLNA	Local Lymph Node Assay
LPS	Lipopolysaccharide
MOA	Mode of Action
MWCNT	Multi Wall Carbon Nanotubes
NOAEL	No Observed Adverse Effect Level

NOCCA	Nordic Occupational Cancer Study
NTP	National Toxicology Program
ODTS	Organic Dust Toxic Syndrome
OECD	Organisation for Economic Co-operation and Development
ORE	Occupational Related Exposure
PAH	Polycyclic Aromatic Hydrocarbon
PAS	Per-Arnt-Sim
PBDD	Polybrominated dibenzo-p-dioxin
PBDE	Polybrominated diphenyl ethers
PBDF	Polybrominated dibenzo-p-furan
PBPK	Physiologically Based Pharmacokinetic/Pharmacodynamic modelling
PBTK	Physiologically Based Toxicokinetic modelling
PCB	Polychlorinated Biphenyls
PCDD	Polychlorinated Dibenzodioxins
PCDF	Polychlorinated Dibenzofurans
PCN	Polychlorinated naphthalenes
PCP	Pentachlorophenol
PFOS	Perfluoro-octanesulfonate
POP	Persistent Organic Pollutant
PXDD	Mixed polychlorinated and polybrominated dibenzo-p-dioxins
PXDF	Mixed polychlorinated and polybrominated dibenzo-p-furans
REACH	Registration, Evaluation, Authorisation and Restriction of Chemical substances
ROAT	Repeated Open Application Test
ROS	Reactive Oxygen Species
RPF	Relative Potency Factors
RSM	Response Surface Methodologies
SCCNFD	Scientific Committee on Cosmetic Products and Non-Food Products
SCCP	Scientific Committee on Consumer Products
SCHER	Scientific Committee on Health and Environmental Risks
SWCNT	Single wall carbon nanotubes
TCDD	2,3,7,8-Tetrachlorodibenzodioxin
TDI	Tolerable Daily Intake
TDS	Testicular Dysgenesis Syndrome
TEF	Toxic Equivalency Factors
TEQ	Toxic Equivalent
TGD	Technical Guidance Documents
TK	Toxicokinetics
TLV	Threshold Limit Value
TNF	Tumour Necrosis Factor
US EPA	US Environmental Protection Agency
WHO	World Health Organization

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